

IPPT_TWINN - Reinforcing the scientific excellence and innovation capacity
in polymer processing technologies
of the Faculty of Polymer Technology

WP1 – ADVANCED HYBRID PROCESSING
TECHNOLOGIES FOR FUTURE DEMANDS

D1.1 MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF THE BONDING STRENGTH BETWEEN THE COMPONENTS

PROJECT: 101079051 — IPPT_TWINN — HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03

VERSION 1.0

Date of delivery: 24.6.2024

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Funded by
the European Union

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Project details

Project Number	101079051
Project Acronym	IPPT_TWINN
Project Name	Reinforcing the scientific excellence and innovation capacity in polymer processing technologies of the Faculty of Polymer Technology
Starting date	1 st January 2023
Duration in months	36
Call (part) identifier	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03
Action	Twining - Institutional networking

Document details

Work Package	WP1
Task	T1.1
Deliverable number	D1.1 Mathematical model of the bonding strength between the components
Version	v1
File name	D1.1 Mathematical model of the bonding strength between the components
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Work package leader	FTPO
Task leader	FTPO
Author	Dr. Béla Zink; Szabolcs Hajagos, Péter Széplaki
Due date	30. 6. 2024.
Submission Date	24. 6. 2024

Version management

Revision history and quality check			
Version	Name	Date	Comment

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Executive summary

Plastic consumption is surging, resulting in higher waste and CO₂ emissions. To address this issue, the IPPT_TWINN project aims to develop more durable products and employ cleaner processing methods. Through collaboration with partners across Europe, including workshops and research initiatives, the project will advance polymer processing knowledge. This collective effort is expected to yield more publications, positioning FTPO as a valuable partner for both academic institutions and industries. Furthermore, the project emphasizes training young researchers in proposal preparation and partnership building, ensuring a robust foundation for future advancements.

The main objective of work package 1 (WP1), titled Advanced hybrid processing technologies for future demands, is to create a hybrid technology for producing high-performance multicomponent structures with a recyclable thermoplastic matrix. This innovative approach combines the strengths of thermoplastic resin transfer molding (T-RTM) and/or injection molding with additive manufacturing in a single production process. By integrating these techniques, the project seeks to enhance efficiency and sustainability in multipart component manufacturing. Given WP consists of 5 tasks, namely Study of the interfacial bonding strength (T1.1), Synthesis of covalent adaptable networks (CANs) using reactive extrusion and compounding (T1.2), Study of improvement of interfacial bonding strength between different polymers (T1.3), Use of CAN in hybrid technologies (T1.4) and Development of demonstrators (T1.5).

The purpose of task T1.1 was to investigate which processing parameters significantly affect the bonding strength of overmolded parts and enhance the bonding strength by modifying the surface structure of the substrate. We started the investigation of the bonding strength by designing a specimen to test the bonding strength by tensile testing. We decided to have a “T-shaped” specimen, consisting of a substrate (flat baseplate), injection molded prior to the overmolding, and an overmolded plate on the substrate. We designed an injection mold for the overmolding and the tensile testing. Processing parameters like mold and melt temperature, preheating temperature etc., were investigated first. After that, we developed a plasma unit to modify the surface structure of the substrate and enhance its bonding strength.

We investigated the overmolding of 3D-printed substrates and overprinting of injection-molded baseplates made of amorphous and semi-crystalline materials. We investigated the effect of printing parameters (e.g., printing speed, layer height, etc.), surface roughness, infill density, local infill density change, fiber reinforcement, and mechanical interlocking on the bonding strength. We used Fused Filament Fabrication and Selective Laser Sintering technologies for printing. Based on the measurement results, we proposed several processing methods to achieve higher bonding strength using the combination of injection molding and additive manufacturing.

Furthermore, our goal in this task was to create a novel healing and bonding strength calculation method. This was achieved by combining finite element method calculation of injection overmolding, analytical modelling of reptation calculation, and element deletion method. First, we summarized the assumptions, neglects, and inadequacies of the already existing calculation methods. After this we created the first version of our calculation method, which we verified for amorphous polymers. Amorphous polymers were used because the healing process of amorphous materials is simpler to model. The novelty of this methodology is that it considers the space-time dependency of the interface temperature. In the next step of development, we combined the analytical modeling of reptation, the numerical modeling of overmolding, and the modeling of tensile tests. We used multiple amorphous polymers to verify calculated results with measurement data. In the last step we proved that our calculation model can be used for semi-crystalline materials by introducing the limit temperatures

when healing starts and stops. We verified these calculation results with data obtained from tensile testing.

Introduction

The combination of additive manufacturing and injection molding can provide higher quality, lightweight polymer parts. In these parts, the reinforcing structure is produced by additive manufacturing and is only placed in the directions in which forces are applied on the part. This preform is overmolded by injection molding, providing excellent surface quality and high precision. High-quality bonding between the preform and the overmolded part is key to achieve the necessary mechanical properties. Bonding between coupled thermoplastic parts in all processing technologies is governed by fusion, resulting from heat and pressure applied to the interface for a certain time [1-5]. Consequently, the bonding strength (σ) between thermoplastic parts is typically a function of processing temperature (T), holding pressure (p), and processing time (t):

$$\sigma = f(T, p, t) \quad (1)$$

One of the most attractive hybrid thermoplastic composite material processes for automotive applications combines thermoforming or injection molding as the first step and injection molding as the second step [6-7]. The bonding strength between the substrate and overmolded elements depends on injection molding parameters such as melt and mold temperature (T_{melt} and T_{mold}), holding pressure, and holding time (p_{hold} and t_{hold}). Studies have shown that increasing the melt temperature, and sometimes mold temperature, strengthens the adhesion between substrates and overmolded elements, while the effect of holding pressure and injection rate is minimal [8-12].

Simulations in process design require a solid mathematical background for each phenomenon occurring during the process. While injection molding is well understood and several computer-aided engineering (CAE) packages are available for modeling it [13-15], the simulation of bonding strength between the substrate and overmolded elements is not included in these packages. The theoretical foundation of bonding involves contact and healing, with healing (or autohesion) being the interdiffusion of polymer molecules across the bonding interface, starting when the temperature rises above the glass transition temperature (T_g) or the melt temperature (T_m) in semi-crystalline thermoplastics [16-18].

The reptation theory, introduced by de Gennes in the 1970s [17], describes the healing process of thermoplastics. It posits that macromolecules are surrounded by a "tube," and as temperature rises above T_g or T_m , the molecule chains leave the tube, enabling bonding. The reptation theory is particularly useful for describing the bonding between the same thermoplastic polymers during overmolding. The time a molecule chain takes to escape from its tube, known as reptation time, is crucial for this theory (1. Figure).

1. Figure Reptation movement of a linear polymer chain, and reptation time, in which the whole chain escapes from the original tube, t_w is the welding time, t_R is the reptation time [17]

Several mathematical models based on reptation theory have been developed to describe the healing process and estimate bonding strength [17, 19-24]. Some of these models assume uniform temperature distribution, which is not the case in overmolding. The models use the degree of healing (D_h), which is the ratio of bonding strength to maximal bonding strength and is a function of time and reptation time:

$$D_h = \frac{\sigma_b}{\sigma_\infty} = f(t_i, t_{rep}(T)) \quad (2)$$

where σ_b is the bonding strength, σ_∞ is the strength of a single-piece part, t_i is the time in a particular step, and t_{rep} is the reptation time at temperature T .

Approaches to model the formation of the interface during overmolding have been proposed, considering different process parameters and their effects on bonding strength [9, 11, 12, 26-28]. However, these models often fail to account for the uneven temperature distribution at the interface, which significantly impacts the degree of healing.

Injection molding is a well-established field of simulation [1-5], with several CAE packages available. However, no existing software models the bond strength between a substrate and an overmolded component due to the complexity of bonding formation, which involves mechanical interlocking, molecular diffusion, electrostatic interaction, and chemical bonding [25].

Two additional phenomena should be considered in the simulation of bond strength: the non-uniform distribution of the degree of healing across the interface and the resulting progressive damage under load. Progressive damage modeling (PDM) methods are used to trace damage propagation up to rupture in polymers [29] and composite materials [30]. PDM generally includes stress analysis, failure analysis, and the calculation of deteriorating material properties. Despite the numerous PDM methods proposed over the past few decades [31], no single method is suitable for all materials. One of the simplest PDM methods within conventional FEM is the element deletion method (EDM) [32]. In EDM, rather than deleting an element, the stress in the element is set to zero once it reaches its ultimate stress [33]. EDM is more convergent than other PDM methods and requires less computing power [34]. It can be effectively used for numerical modeling of crack propagation [33] and failure progression [34] in composites.

Methods, materials, and equipment used

1.1. Materials

We used acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) Terluran GP35 (INEOS Styrolution Group GmbH, Germany), polycarbonate (PC) Makrolon 2205 (Covestro AG, Switzerland), and polystyrene (PS) Edistir N 3910 (Versalis S.p.A., Italy) in the injection molding and overmolding experiments of amorphous polymer materials. We performed the main testing on ABS, PC, and PS to show that the method also works with other amorphous polymers. For the testing and modeling of semi-crystalline materials, we used two different types of polypropylene (PP), homopolymer Tipplen H145F (MOL Petrochemicals Co. Ltd., Hungary) and random copolymer Tipplen R959A (MOL Petrochemicals Co. Ltd., Hungary) PP.

Material	ABS	PC	PS	PA6	PP	
Type	Terluran GP35	Makrolon 2205	Edistir N 3910	Lanxess Durethan B30S	Tipplen H154F	Tipplen R959A
Drying temperature and time	80 °C for 4 h	120 °C for 2-3 h	not required	80 °C for 4 h	not required	not required
Recommended melt temperature range	220-260 °C	290-300 °C	200-250 °C	260-280 °C	190-235 °C	180-230 °C
Recommended mold temperature range	30-60 °C	80-120 °C	10-50 °C	80-100 °C	20-80 °C	20-80 °C
Utilized melt temperature	220, 240, 260, 280 °C	300, 320, 340 °C	200, 220, 240, 260, 280 °C	220, 240, 260, 280, 300 °C	190, 210, 230, 250 °C	
Utilized mold temperature	40, 60 °C	100 °C	40 °C	40, 80 °C	40 °C	

1. Table Drying and molding recommendation for the used materials

For the 3D printing 3D printing and injection overmolded parts adhesion tests, Since the goal was to combine the advantages of injection molding and 3D printing, for these experiments we chose materials that can be processed by both technologies. The types and manufacturers of the used materials are shown in 1. Table.

Name	Type	Trade Name	Manufacturer	Abbreviation
Injection molding				
Acrylonitrile-butadiene styrene	Pellets	Terluran ABS GP35	INEOS Styrolution Group GmbH	ABS GP35
Fused deposition modelling				
Polyamide 12	Filament	Nylon FX256	Filamentum	PA FX256
Selective laser sintering				
Polyamide 12	Powder	PA2200	EOS GmbH	PA2200
Reinforcement				
Carbon fiber	Chopped fiber length: 6 mm	Zoltek PX35	Zoltek	PX35

2. Table Materials used for 3D printing and injection overmolded parts adhesion tests

The nylon filament (PA FX256) was a commercially available and used to manufacture the FFF specimens. Their properties were defined by the manufacturer and are shown in the 2. Table.

To print with ABS, I have selected ABS GP35 (Terluran GP35, INEOS Styrolution, Germany) as our primary material because we wanted to use the same material as for injection molding. First, the ABS pellets were dried at 80 °C for four hours. Then, the filaments with a diameter of about 1.75 mm were extruded with a twin-screw extruder (LTE 26-44, LabTech Scientific, Thailand). The temperature profile of the extruder was 210 °C, 215 °C, 220 °C, 225 °C, 230 °C (from the feed section to the die). The screw rpm was 80 1/min.

The unsintered powder (PA2200) was supplied by VARINEX Zrt., Hungary and was prepared from recycled PA12 filament. Their properties were tabulated in the 2. Table. First, the powder was subjected to extrusion granulation by LZ-120/VS Granulator (Labtech Engineering Co., Ltd., Thailand). Then the obtained pellets were extruded and drawn by a twin-screw extruder (LTE 26-44, Labtech Scientific, Thailand). The temperatures were 175 °C in the first zone, 180 °C in the second zone, 185 °C in the third zone, 190 °C in the fourth zone and again 190 °C for the head. The filament diameter was controlled at approximately 1.75 mm, and finally, the drawn filament was rolled on a spool.

1.2. Injection molding machines

In our preliminary experiments, we used an Arburg Allrounder Advance 270S 400-170 (ARBURG GmbH, Lossburg, Germany) injection molding machine. The temperature of the aluminum prototype mold was measured with a Flir A325 SC thermal camera. For manufacturing preforms and T-shaped test specimens, we used an Arburg Allrounder 370S 700-250 injection molding machine. For temperature control of the injection molds, we employed a Wittmann TempPro Plus 90 (WITTMANN Technology GmbH, Austria) temperature control unit.

1.3. Dryers

We processed the injection moldable PA6 materials using a closed system consisting of a Motan Luxor 50 (Motan Colortronic Ltd., United Kingdom) dry air dryer and a vacuum feeder. We used a Faithful WGLL-125 BE (Huanghua Faithful Instrument Co., LTD, China) hot air-drying oven for pre-production drying of other injection molding materials. The drying temperature and duration were determined according to the manufacturer's datasheet: PA6 (80 °C, 4 hours), ABS (80 °C, 3 hours), PC (120 °C, 3 hours), PLA (80 °C, 6 hours).

1.4. T-RTM machine

We produced the T-RTM preforms using Engel Insert 200V/200H/80 two-component injection molding machine and D60 (Engel Austria GmbH, Austria) single-component (with one in-situ dispenser and one mixing head) T-RTM unit.

1.5. Plasma treatment

For our plasma treatment investigations, we developed our own plasma treatment unit. We generated plasma from compressed air using the FG 5001 (Plasmatreat GmbH, Germany) plasma generator. The pressure of the compressed air was reduced to the manufacturer-recommended level (3.5 bar) using a pressure regulator. The reduced pressure compressed air was directed into a Plasmatreat RD1004 rotary plasma head. Parameters affecting the plasma properties (voltage, current) were adjusted on the control unit. The plasma head was mounted on the frame of a K8200 3D printer (Velleman Group, Belgium). The preforms were secured to the 3D printer's build plate. The movement of the build plate was controlled by a computer, with a maximum speed of 6000 mm/min.

1.6. Contact Angle Measurement

To assess the wettability of the preforms after plasma treatment, contact angle measurements were conducted according to ISO/TS 14778:2021 using a DSA 30 (Krüss, Germany) drop shape analyzer. Three drops (10 µl/drop) of millipore (high purity) water were used for each preform to determine the advancing contact angle. The room temperature was 25 °C and the relative humidity in the measuring cell was 80%.

1.7. X-ray Diffraction (XRD)

The surface of the injection molded PA6, raw preforms was examined using an X-ray diffraction instrument X'PERT PRO (Panalytical Ltd., United Kingdom). Measurements were performed on the Cu K α line, with 1.54 Å radiation, using a copper anode X-ray tube with 40 kV and 30 mA tube parameters, over a measurement range of $2\theta = 2-46^\circ$.

1.8. X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS)

The surface of the injection-molded ABS samples was analyzed using an X-ray twin-anode X-ray source (XR4, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and a hemispherical energy analyzer with a 9-channel detector (Phoibos 150 MCD, SPECS). The base pressure of the analyzer chamber was 2×10^{-9} mbar, with a measurement sensitivity of 0.1%.

1.9. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

Differential scanning calorimetry tests were performed using a TA Instruments DSC Q2000 device.

Samples weighing 4 ± 0.5 mg were placed in aluminum sample holders, covered with lids, and crimped. Nitrogen was used as the measuring medium to avoid sample degradation. For PA6 samples, a heat-cool-heat program was conducted at 10 °C/min within a temperature range of 25 - 250 °C. For PLA samples, the program was conducted at 5 °C/min within a temperature range of 0 - 200 °C. The results of the DSC measurements were used to compare the samples with each other.

For the 3D printing tests, a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) was used to analyze the samples' specific heat, crystallization temperature, and crystallinity. We have characterized the thermal properties using differential scanning calorimetry in the DSC Q2000 instrument (TA Instruments, United States) for the prepared filaments. First, a small specimen of 4.5 mg was cut and placed in an aluminum pan. The specimen was heated from room temperature to 250 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min under a nitrogen atmosphere.

1.10. Surface Roughness Measurement

For the purely injection molding overmolding methods, the surface roughness of different ABS preforms was measured using a Mitutoyo SJ-400 (Mitutoyo, Japan) device, according to the EN ISO 4287:1998 standard. During measurement, the diamond stylus moved at a speed of 1 mm/second for both measurement and return. Care was taken to ensure the stylus applied consistent pressure to the surface, adjusted via the scale on the device display. The device measured the average surface roughness (R_a) and the height of surface irregularities (R_z). Measurements were conducted on 9 areas of each specimen and mold insert, with 3 repetitions each. The surface roughness and irregularity height of the plates and inserts were determined by averaging the results.

For the 3D printing and injection overmolded parts adhesion tests, we have measured the surface roughness (R_a) of the preforms with a contact-based surface roughness profilometer on the same Mitutoyo SJ 400 (2. Figure). The different printing parameters resulted in different R_a values. Measurements were made from 3 different points in a rectangular of 3×8 mm in the centre of base plates where the contact area is during the overmolding process (2. Figure). In addition, the area surface roughness (S_a) of printed preforms was measured with a wide-area 3D measurement system (Keyence VR-5000, Keyence Corp., Japan). With the help of this system, we have also performed imaging of certain microstructures created on the base plates.

2. Figure Surface roughness probe touching the base plate and the measurement lines

1.11. Injection molding processing conditions and test samples

We designed a new geometry for the test specimen, a so-called “rib-on-plate geometry” (3. Figure), to characterize the overmolding process. This test specimen consists of an 80 mm \times 80 mm \times 2 mm base

plate, which we manufactured separately by conventional injection molding with a melt temperature of 260 °C and a mold temperature of 60 °C.

3. Figure The test sample for investigating the bonding strength of overmolded parts

The other part of the test specimen is a 70 mm × 63 mm × 2 mm overmolded rib produced by injection molding. The base plate was created with an Arburg Allrounder Advance 270S 400-170 (ARBURG GmbH, Germany) injection molding machine, and the rib was overmolded with an Arburg Allrounder 470 A 1000-290 (ARBURG GmbH, Germany) injection molding machine. For manufacturing the overmolded elements, we developed a mold, which is equipped with a mechanically operated slider to accommodate the base plate. To control the switchover position, we installed a Cavity Eye RC15 pressure sensor into the wall of the mold. The pressure sensor was installed 10 mm before the contact interface. Switchover occurred when melt pressure reached 4 MPa. The resulting filling time, further used for simulations, was 0.6 s. The holding pressure was set to 75 MPa for 2.2 s, and the remaining cooling time was 20 s. After removing the sprue from the part, we investigated the interface that formed between the two components.

4. Figure The injection mold used to produce the base plates and the overmolded specimens, furthermore the tensile mount used in the testing

The average cycle time for overmolding was slightly above 50 seconds. For the testing the influence of base plate temperature, the plates were kept in the closed mold for 20 seconds at 40 and 80 °C. We set up a flow rate of 40 cm³/s for the injection phase. The switchover position was controlled through an internal pressure transducer placed close to the end of the cavity. We used 75 MPa for 2 seconds for the holding phase. The parts were ejected after a residual cooling time of 22 seconds. The parts were kept at room temperature for 6 hours before the tensile tests.

With the same injection molding parameters for the 3D printing tests, we have also produced the CF-reinforced ABS pellets by manually mixing ABS GP35 pellets with 15 wt% 6 mm long CF (PX 35, Zoltek,

Hungary). The mix was extruded with a twin-screw extruder (LTE 26-44, LabTech Scientific, Thailand). The processing temperature was in the range of 185-225 °C, and the screw speed was 80 1/min. The CF/ABS extruded strands were cooled with a cooling fan and pelletized into approximately 3 mm long granules and then dried.

The unsintered PA2200 was subjected to extrusion granulation by LZ-120/VS Granulator (Labtech Scientific, Thailand). First, the powder was extruded and drawn, and then the obtained filament was subjected to extrusion granulation. The same machines used before to prepare PA12 filament were used to prepare the pellets.

After the FFF preforms were cooled, we injection molded the dried pellets on them (ABS or CF reinforced ABS) with an Arburg Allrounder 270S 400-170 (ARBURG GmbH, Germany). For the overmolding of the printed parts, we used the same mold as in the previous purely injection molding experiments (4. Figure), which can accommodate the 80 mm x 80 mm x 2 mm preforms and create a rib in the middle. The shape of the final overmolded part is shown in 5. Figure. It consists of a base plate and an overmolded rib. The mold can also be used without inserting a base plate to manufacture the reference specimen in which both elements (a base plate and a rib) are injection-molded together in one shot.

5. Figure Geometry of overmolded specimen for the 3D printing adhesion tests

Similarly, four different combinations of overmolding and overprinting processes were identified and shown in 2. Table.

3. Table Four different combinations of overmolding and overprinting

1.12. FFF and SLS Printing

We have produced 80 mm x 80 mm x 2 mm base plates (6. Figure) from the in-house prepared ABS filament, PA FX256 and in-house prepared PA filament. We printed the base plates using an FFF printer (Craftbot plus, CraftUnique Ltd., Hungary).

6. Figure Geometry of preforms (baseplate)

A similar base plates was also sintered with PA2200 powder in an EOS P396 (EOS GmbH, Germany) SLS printer. The laser sintering system works with CO₂ laser type with 70 W laser power. The used PA2200 powders were spread on the powder bed with the bed temperature set to 168 °C, and the part began to build with 100 μm layer thickness. After the sintering process was finished, the specimens were cooled to room temperature in the building chamber and taken out from the residual powder.

1.13. Mechanical testing

For the tensile tests, we used a Zwick Z020 (Zwick Roell Group, Germany) universal tensile testing machine with a load cell limit of ±20 kN. For the rib-on-plate test specimen, we developed a grip (7.

Figure). The upper holder plate of the grip has a 3 mm wide slot in the middle, where we placed the rib of the specimen. The rib was clamped with the conventional grip at the bottom. Testing speed was 5 mm/min, and we tested 5 specimens for each set of processing parameter combination.

7. Figure The geometry and functioning of the tensile grip used to test bonding strength

1.14. Flash DSC

We performed flash DSC (Flash DSC 1, Switzerland) tests to investigate the crystallization properties of the materials. Several cooling and heating rates were used in the tests.

1.15. Rheological testing

The reptation time at given temperatures is needed for the calculation of bonding strength. It can be assumed that the reptation time is equal to the relaxation time of the polymer at a given temperature. The relaxation time at a specific temperature is the time after which the elastic modulus (G') of the polymer is equal to its storage modulus (G''), and it is the reciprocal of the angular frequency. We ran a frequency sweep test on the samples using a parallel plate rotational rheometer (AR2000, TA Instruments, United States) to find the angular frequency. The shear strain applied was 0.5 %, the diameter of the plates was 25 mm, and their thickness was 1.2 mm. These samples were manufactured on an Arburg Allrounder 270S (ARBURG GmbH, Germany) injection molding machine. The plates were cut from injection molded specimens.

We calculated the reptation time from the reciprocal of the first crossover frequency of the elastic modulus (G') and storage modulus (G''):

$$t_{rep}(T) = \frac{1}{\omega_{1X}(T)} \quad (3)$$

where $t_{rep}(T)$ is the reptation time, $\omega_{1X}(T)$ is the first crossover frequency.

We fitted the Williams-Landel-Ferry (WLF) equation on the measured values.

$$\log a_T(T) = \frac{C_1(T-T_{ref})}{C_2+(T-T_{ref})} \quad (4)$$

$$a_T(T) = \frac{t_{rep}(T)}{t_{rep,ref}} \quad (5)$$

where $a_T(T)$ is the shift factor, t_{rep} is the reptation time at temperature T , T_{ref} is the reference temperature, C_1 and C_2 are fitting constants.

1.16. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

For the 3D printing tests, we performed thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) using the TGA Q500

instrument (TA Instruments, United States) in a nitrogen atmosphere. The test started from room temperature to 600 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min.

1.17. Fourier transform infrared analysis (FTIR)

We performed the Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) analysis to identify the molecular structure of the virgin PA12 filament, recycled PA12 filament and unsintered PA 2200 powder. I prepared 20 mm x 20 mm samples from each material and analyzed the Attenuated Total Reflectance (ATR) with a Tensor II Type FTIR Spectrometer (Bruker, USA). All the thermal measurements were used to identify critical process parameters (FFF bed temperature, IM melt temperature, LS sintering window) and better understand the selected materials.

1.18. Thermal imaging

In order to reveal the absolute temperature distribution for the 3D printing tests, an infrared (IR) camera was used. When the base plate was being printed in the FFF machine, the temperature was recorded to measure the temperature variation between the FFF bed and the base plate and their relation with the cooling fan. A FLIR A325SC IR (Teledyne FLIR LLC, _USA) camera with 320x240 resolution was used with an emission factor of 0.95. Its reported accuracy was ± 2 °C, it was used in conjunction with the FLIR ThermaCAM Researcher Pro software.

Experimental results

In this section we introduce our modelling methodologies, results and conclusions for the investigation and modification of bonding strength and development of bonding strength modelling methodology.

2. Overmolding of injection molded parts

In the first part we introduce the result of the effects of processing parameters on the bonding strength. Furthermore, we present the results of plasma treatment on the bonding strength.

2.1. Melt, mold and preheating temperature

We investigated the effect of melt temperature, mold temperature and waiting time on bonding strength for ABS overmolded on ABS preform (ABS/ABS). We used the injection mold to preheat the preform before overmolding. The time for preheating (waiting time) was chosen to be the time between closing the tool and overmolding, which we set to 0 and 30 seconds based on our preliminary experiments. Based on our calculations, we expected that with a waiting time of 30 seconds, the preform would be heated to the mold temperature throughout its cross-section. We varied the melt temperature between 220 and 300 °C in 20 °C steps. We chose the mold temperature to be a lower (40 °C) and higher (80 °C) value based on the manufacturer's recommended temperature range. The holding pressure was 450 bar, and the holding time was 4 seconds. The bonding strength increased in the material's recommended processing range (220-260 °C) as the mold temperature increased. At 280 and 300 °C melt temperatures, neither the preheating time nor the mold temperature significantly affected bonding strength (8. Figure). Therefore, the higher average tensile strength observed at these melt temperatures is probably due to the larger amount of heat introduced to the interface. However, within the recommended processing range, the preform heats up better with a 30-second waiting time than 0 seconds. The temperature of the interface gets closer to the glass transition (T_g) temperature (~105 °C) - it can get into the melt state faster - the molecular chains have more time to intertwine, so higher bonding strength can be achieved.

8. Figure Tensile strength for ABS/ABS specimens (ABS preform overmolded by ABS) produced with different melt temperature, T_{sz} – mold temperature, t_v – waiting time

We also performed our experiments with PA6 overmolded on PA6 preforms (PA6/PA6) with a longer waiting time (30 seconds) (9. Figure) (450 bar holding pressure, 4 seconds holding time). We also manufactured one-piece injection molded specimens as a reference. In the case of overmolding, the average tensile strength of the joint increased with increasing melt temperature due to the increasing amount of heat input, so the molecular chains had more time to intertwine during cooling from a higher temperature than at lower melt temperatures. The melt temperatures of 240 and 250 °C are below the

recommended processing range of the material (260-280 °C), which resulted in a significantly weaker bond due to the lower amount of heat input.

9. Figure Tensile strength for PA6/PA6 (PA6 preform overmolded by PA6) and PA6 (injection molded PA6) specimens produced with different melt temperature

We preheated the preforms in a drying oven in several steps between 80 and 230 °C for 20 minutes. Five seconds elapsed between opening the oven and overmolding the 270 °C melt. The average tensile strength increases with the temperature of the preform up to a limit of around 140 °C and then starts to decrease (10. Figure). This decrease may have been caused by the degradation of the surface of the test pieces, which was indicated by the brown color visible on the surface upon removal from the oven, which became darker with increasing temperature (170, 200, 230 °C). This phenomenon can be reduced by minimizing the time spent in the oven. With 140 °C preheating, we achieved an average tensile strength increase of 30-40% compared to the result preheated with a normal 80 °C tool (10. Figure). This means it is worth considering the justification of preheating under given production conditions. A preheating device could reduce the results' standard deviation, bringing the time between the end of preheating and the start of overmolding to the same time for each preform.

10. Figure Tensile strength for PA6/PA6 (PA6 preform overmolded by PA6) specimens produced with different preheating temperature, T_{sz} – mold temperature, T_{δ} – melt temperature

2.2. Holding pressure

We investigated the effect of holding pressure on bonding strength in the case of ABS overmolded on ABS preform (ABS/ABS) (11. Figure). We analyzed the average tensile strength values of the four holding pressures using variance analysis. Based on the results ($p=0.404$), we can say that the holding pressure has no significant effect on the strength of the bond when using a mold temperature of 40 °C and a melt temperature of 240 °C.

11. Figure Effect of holding pressure on the average tensile strength of ABS/ABS specimens, T_{sz} – mold temperature, T_{δ} – melt temperature

2.3. Degree of crystallinity of preforms

For our investigations, we chose a wider range of tool temperatures (40, 60, 80, 100, 120 °C) and melt temperatures (240, 260, 280, 300 °C) than the manufacturer's recommendation. We aimed to influence the crystalline content of the material to the greatest possible extent with the different mold temperatures. We carried out overmolding and the injection molding of the one-piece reference samples at a melt temperature of 280 °C and a mold temperature of 80 °C (holding pressure was 450 bar, holding time was 4 seconds). The average tensile strength of the one-piece reference test pieces was 58.0 ± 1.5 MPa. According to the results of PA6/PA6 overmolding, the average tensile strength decreases (12. Figure) with increasing mold temperature used for injection molding of the preform - regardless of the melt temperature.

12. Figure Effect of mold temperature on the average tensile strength of the overmolded rib, preforms produced with different mold and melt temperatures, $T_{sz-ráfr.}$ – mold temperature of preform production, $T_{\delta-ráfr.}$ – melt temperature of preform production, T_{δ} – melt temperature of overmolding

Based on the results, we assumed that the change in interfacial strength is caused by the change in the crystalline content of the surface layer, so we performed DSC measurements on samples taken from the surface of the preforms. We removed 0.1 ± 0.05 mm thick slices from the surface layer with a low-speed mill. The temperature of the machining environment (30 ± 3 °C) was measured with a thermal camera. The time required for one DSC measurement was approximately 80 minutes, so one day elapsed between the measurement of the first and last sample of the measurement series. When evaluating our DSC measurements, we determined the baseline using the Khanna and Kuhn method. We took the melting enthalpy for 100% theoretical crystalline content of PA6 as the 230 J/g. Based on the results, there is no significant difference either in the crystalline contents measured during the first

or second heating, or in the crystalline contents belonging to the individual technological settings (4. Table). Based on this result, the change in interfacial strength cannot be explained by the change in crystalline content.

X_c (%)		T_{sz} (°C)				
		40	60	80	100	120
$T_{\bar{o}}$ (°C)	240	28.7	30.3	29.2	29.5	28.8
	260	29.9	29.5	28.7	29.5	28.5
	280	28.2	28.8	28.7	29.4	27.9
	300	30.2	29.0	29.2	28.9	28.4

$X_{c,2}$ (%)		T_{sz} (°C)				
		40	60	80	100	120
$T_{\bar{o}}$ (°C)	240	28.5	31.1	29.7	30.3	30.4
	260	30.7	30.7	30.4	29.8	28.9
	280	28.7	30.9	29.1	29.8	28.3
	300	31.3	29.9	29.5	30.2	31.0

4. Table The degree of crystallinity for the first X_c (a) and the second $X_{c,2}$ (b) heating

Since the crystalline content did not change on the surface of the preforms manufactured with the investigated technological settings, we assumed that the structure of the different crystalline modifications forming the crystalline content could be responsible for the different interfacial strengths. We investigated the ratio of amorphous and crystalline parts formed on the surface of PA6 with X-ray diffraction (XRD), as well as the different crystalline modifications (α , γ) of the crystalline parts (13. Figure). Based on the XRD results, we can say that the ratio of the crystalline modifications to each other on the surface of the preforms changes as a function of the mold temperature. At low mold temperatures (40, 60, 80 °C), the γ crystalline modification ($2\theta=21.38^\circ$) dominates. With increasing mold temperature, the amount of the γ crystalline modification decreased, while the amount of the α ($2\theta=20.0^\circ$ and 23.7°) crystalline modifications increased. Regarding strength results, the samples overmolded on preforms containing more γ crystalline modification are stronger. This can be explained by the fact that the γ crystalline modification has lower strength and melting temperature than the α crystalline modifications, so less heat is required to melt it. Therefore, when manufacturing preforms for PA6 overmolding, the technological settings (e.g. low mold temperature) should be chosen so that as much γ crystalline modification as possible is formed on the surface.

13. Figure Results of XRD of preforms produced with different mold temperatures

2.4. Surface roughness

To investigate the effect of surface roughness, we injection-molded preforms with different surface roughnesses using the mold inserts (polished, fine spark-eroded, coarse spark-eroded). We used ABS for producing preforms and overmolded ribs.

We first investigated whether the surface roughness of preforms is influenced by melt (220, 240, 260, 280 °C) and mold temperature (40, 60, 80 °C). We used the following constant parameters for the different series: 30 cm³/s injection speed, 450 bar holding pressure, 4 seconds holding time and 15 seconds residual cooling time. After injection molding, we stored the preforms at room temperature in 50% relative humidity air, and then measured their surface roughness (R_a , R_z) within 4-6 hours. We found that neither the melt temperature nor the tool temperature significantly affected the surface roughness formed on the preforms in the investigated range. Therefore, we manufactured the preforms at the average values of the recommended processing range (melt temperature of 240 °C, mold temperature of 60 °C).

We assumed that the surface quality of the preforms could also be influenced by the magnitude of the holding pressure. This can be investigated most straightforward on the preform with the highest surface roughness, so we injection-molded preforms with the coarse spark-eroded mold insert at the average values of the recommended processing range of the material ($T_{\delta}=240$ °C, $T_{sz}=60$ °C). We chose a long, 15 seconds holding time for the three different holding pressures (150, 300, 450 bar). Based on the variance analysis performed on our results ($p=0.701$), we found (14. Figure) that in the case of the preform with the highest surface roughness, the back pressure has no significant effect on the surface roughness of the preform in the investigated range. Therefore, in the following, we set the holding pressure to 80% of the injection pressure (maximum pressure during filling phase) for the manufacture of the preforms, and we used the fine spark-eroded (middle of the three different surface roughnesses) mold inserts to produce the preforms.

14. Figure Surface roughness of the preforms manufactured using the roughest mold insert in the case of different holding pressures

For overmolding, we used the preforms made with the fine spark-eroded mold inserts using the manufacturing technology presented previously. We assumed that during the time between placing the preform in the mold and the overmolding, the mold heats up the preform, so the higher tool temperature value can positively affect the strength of the bond that develops. We overmolded a rib onto the preforms with different mold and melt temperature settings ($T_{\delta}= 240, 260, 280, 300$ °C, $T_{sz}= 40, 60, 80$ °C) to investigate this assumption. 15. Figure shows the change in average tensile strength as a function of melt temperature. We analyzed the results by variance analysis by melt temperature group (220, 240, 260, 280 °C). We found that the mold temperature significantly affects the average tensile strength at lower melt temperatures (240 and 260 °C).

15. Figure The effect of melt temperature on the average tensile strength of specimens one-piece injection molded and overmolded with different mold temperatures, T_{sz} – mold temperature

Furthermore, we assumed that the melt temperature of the overmolded rib influences the bonding strength. Therefore, we overmolded ribs with melt temperatures of 220, 240, 260, 280, 300 °C onto the preforms in a 60 °C tool (16. Figure). In the case of the specimens manufactured with the lowest melt temperature (220 °C), the bond was so weak that the rib could be easily removed from the preform by hand. This was because the melt could transmit too little heat to the preform, so it could not melt it. The average tensile strength increased for all three surface roughnesses with increasing melt temperature. The measurement results show a saturation character.

16. Figure Effect of melt temperature on the average tensile strength between the preform produced with different surface roughnesses and the overmolded rib, T_{sz} – mold temperature

We performed a group variance analysis on the results of each melt temperature. We investigated the effect of surface roughness at a 95% significance level. We found that the effect of the surface roughness of the preform on the bonding strength decreases with increasing melt temperature (17. Figure). The surface roughness affects the bonding strength at lower melt temperatures, but at higher melt temperatures, it does not. This is probably because at lower melt temperatures, the peaks of the roughness do not or only slightly melt under the influence of the small amount of heat transferred to the boundary surface, so the size of the associated surfaces is sufficiently large to establish a measurable relationship.

17. Figure ANOVA results for the melt temperature influence on bonding strength

2.5. Effect of plasma treatment

We chose plasma treatment, a technology that is already partially introduced in the industry, but still novel and under ongoing research, for improving bonding strength. We investigated the connection between amorphous and partially crystalline material pairs overmolded from the same material, as well as materials that are different from each other, observing the effect of plasma treatment.

We prepared preforms using the plasma treatment equipment from ABS and PA6. The plasma treatment was carried out with 3.5 bar compressed air, 280 V voltage and 17.5 A current setting. The central 20 mm wide strip (boundary surface) of the preform was treated by moving the table slowly, medium and fast (1000, 3000, 6000 mm/min) under the plasma head, at a distance of $h=10$ mm commonly used in industrial practice (18. Figure). The plasma treatment was always carried out approximately 30 seconds before overmolding (~ 30 seconds = treatment + transfer + tool closing). In some experiments, the plasma treatment speed and distance differed from the values given here, but these differences are indicated separately for the given experiments.

18. Figure Plasma treatment unit with the main dimensions; 1, plasma head; 2, plasma beam; 3, preform; h : distance between the plasma head and the preform; v : speed of table (plasma treatment speed)

2.6. Overmolding of the same material

2.6.1. Amorphous Material - ABS/ABS overmolding

In the case of ABS/ABS material pairs (19. Figure), we chose small, medium and large (1000, 3000 and 6000 mm/min) values for the plasma treatment speed of the preforms. The melt temperature of the

overmolded ABS was changed between 220 °C and 280 °C in 20 °C increments (holding pressure was 450 bar, holding time was 4 seconds). Reference, untreated T-shaped test pieces were also manufactured by overmolding. In the case of untreated preforms, the average bond strength increases with increasing melt temperature. It reaches its maximum at 280 °C melt temperature (~16 MPa). At plasma treatment speeds of 1000 and 3000 mm/min, the bond strength is lower than that of untreated samples at all melt temperatures. At a plasma treatment speed of 6000 mm/min, the average bond strength was the same as that of untreated samples at all temperatures except the highest temperature. Overall, plasma treatment does not improve the bond between the preform and the overmolded rib in the case of the ABS/ABS material pair. This can be caused by the apolar nature of ABS.

19. Figure Effect of melt temperature on average tensile strength in the case of untreated, one-piece injection molded and plasma treated ABS/ABS specimens, T_{sz} – mold temperature

ABS is apolar, with weak polarizability and a lack of hydrogen bonding sites (H-bond donors/acceptors = 0/1 per monomer unit). Thus, in the case of ABS/ABS bonding, π - π interactions between aromatic units and other weak secondary bonding forces - e.g. dispersion forces, π -dipole- and dipole-dipole interactions – dominate.

Plasma treatment significantly influenced these interactions by chemically modifying the surface of the ABS samples. These changes are mainly oxidation reactions, especially hydroxylations, which make the surface more and more polar. At low plasma treatment speeds, the polarized surface of the ABS preforms resulted in polarity-based incompatibility with the untreated ABS melt. Therefore, plasma treatment does not improve the bonding strength in the case of ABS/ABS material pairs.

2.6.2. Semi-crystalline material - PA6/PA6 overmolding

In the ABS/ABS experiments we observed that the higher speed did not or only slightly deteriorate the bond. Therefore, for the PA6/PA6 material pair, we treated the preforms at a plasma treatment speed of 6000 mm/min and then overmolded them at different melt temperatures (20. Figure).

20. Figure Effect of melt temperature on tensile strength in the case of treated, untreated and one-piece injection molded specimens, T_{sz} – mold temperature, v – plasma head speed

The results for treated and untreated samples show a saturation behavior as a function of melt temperature. For untreated specimens, the average tensile strength reached its maximum at a melt temperature of 300 °C. At temperatures below 290 °C, we observed that plasma treatment significantly improved the bond between PA6 and PA6. This can be explained by the more polar nature of PA6, which is enhanced by plasma treatment. At melt temperatures of 270 and 280 °C, the tensile strength of plasma-treated specimens reaches about 70% of the tensile strength of the one-piece injection molded references.

In the case of the PA6/PA6 bond, dipole-dipole interactions between polymer chains typically provide the bond. In addition, H-bonds, as the strongest secondary bonding forces, can also be formed (H-bond donors/acceptors = 1/2), which allows for the formation of 2 different H-bonds between polymer chains. The new hydroxyl and oxo groups formed because of plasma treatment increase the possibilities for further hydrogen bond formation, which can further increase the bond strength. The higher temperature can provide mobility for the proper arrangement of polymer chains, which can allow for an increase in the number of interactions. These stronger interactions resulted in the increased average tensile strength. We expect that at lower plasma treatment speeds, the more polar nature of PA6 would become even more polar.

2.7. Overmolding of different materials

2.7.1. PA6T-RTM/PA6 Overmolding

We overmolded natural PA6 material onto PA6 preforms manufactured using the TRTM process. The plasma treatment speed was set to 6000 mm/min, similar to the PA6/PA6 experiments. Considering the preform manufacturing technology's uncertainties, we achieved a positive effect with plasma treatment at melt temperatures of 280 °C and 300 °C (21. Figure). The reason for this could be - similarly to PA6/PA6 overmolding - that new hydroxyl and oxo groups appear on the surface of the preform as a result of plasma treatment. In parallel with the development of TRTM technology, it is worth carrying out further overmolding experiments combined with plasma treatment.

21. Figure Effect of melt temperature on the tensile strength of specimens consisting of TRTM manufactured preform overmolded with PA6 ribs, T_{sz} – mold temperature

2.7.2. PA/ABS Overmolding

We prepared untreated and plasma-treated PA6 preforms at different speeds (2000, 4000, 6000 mm/min) and at a distance of 10 mm. We then overmolded ABS onto them at a melt temperature of 260 °C. (holding pressure 450 bar, holding time 4 seconds) No bond was observed between the two components in either treated or untreated cases (22. Figure).

22. Figure Treated and untreated PA6 preforms and the overmolded ribs, ribs separated during ejection, 1, PA6 ptrform; 2, overmolded ABS rib; 3, overmolding injection mold, h – plasma treatment distance, v – plasma head speed

2.7.3. ABS/PA Overmolding

We prepared untreated and plasma-treated ABS preforms, and then overmolded PA6 ribs onto them in the melt temperature range of 240-300 °C with a step of 10 °C, holding pressure and holding time was set to 450 bar and 4 seconds respectively. Plasma treatment was carried out at 2000, 4000, 6000 mm/min speeds and at 4, 6, 8, 10 mm distances (23. Figure). In the untreated case, no bond is formed between the ABS preform and the PA6 rib at all. With plasma treatment, a bond could be formed between the two components. The lower the plasma treatment speed (the longer the treatment time), the stronger the bond formed. Within the recommended processing range of the base material, the strongest bond was formed with plasma treatment at the slowest speed. This bond strength is still significantly lower than that of references made of ABS or PA6 from a single material, but it still demonstrates the potential for creating a bond between incompatible materials using plasma treatment.

23. Figure Changes in the average bond strength of the ABS preform and the injection-molded PA6 rib as a function of the melt temperature and the speed of the plasma treatment (The distance of the plasma treatment was 10 mm.)

The relationship between the plasma treatment distance and the resulting bond strength is not as clear as it was for the plasma treatment speed (24. Figure). With a plasma speed of 2000 mm/min, we did not observe a bond formed at a distance of 4 mm. The surface of the preforms was discolored, and the plasma degraded the surface. However, we were able to form a bond with plasma treatment at distances of 6, 8, and 10 mm.

24. Figure The average bond strength of the bond formed between the plasma-treated ABS preform and the injection-molded PA6 rib as a function of the plasma treatment distance. The speed of plasma treatment is 2000 mm/min

To investigate the cause of the bond formed between the ABS preform and the PA6 rib as a result of plasma treatment, we began by measuring the advancing contact angle on the ABS preforms. We measured the advancing contact angle on three samples for each setting (25. Figure). The untreated value was $87.99^\circ \pm 1.28^\circ$. We were able to continuously reduce this value with plasma treatment at 8 mm distance (based on Figure 96) and at different speeds (2000, 4000, 6000 mm/min), i.e., the surface became increasingly wettable (more polar) as a result of plasma treatment (26. Figure).

25. Figure The maximum contact angle measured on the surface of the ABS preform v: plasma treatment speed

26. Figure The change of the contact angle as a function of the speed of the plasma treatment on ABS specimens, in the case of a treatment distance of 8 mm

We investigated whether there is a correlation between the plasma treatment distance and the maximum advancing contact angle for a treatment speed of 2000 mm/min (based on Figure 95). At a plasma treatment distance of 4 mm, the maximum advancing contact angle is $60.93 \pm 2.26^\circ$, which is smaller than for the untreated case, but still not enough for bonding to occur. At distances of 6, 8, and 10 mm, the results correlate (27. Figure) with the tensile strength results, i.e., at larger distances the contact angle is sufficiently small for bonding to occur.

27. Figure Change of contact angle depending on the distance of the plasma treatment on ABS specimens, at a treatment speed of 2000 mm/min

The results of the contact angle measurements clearly show a difference between untreated and treated preforms. Therefore, we performed XPS measurements on $10 \times 10 \times 2$ mm samples cut from the ABS preforms to investigate the surface chemical composition. 28. Figure shows the overview spectrum of the untreated and plasma-treated samples, where the electron intensity is shown as a function of binding energy.

28. Figure XPS overview spectrum of untreated ABS preform – left, XPS overview spectrum of Plasma treated ($h=10$ mm, $v=6000$ mm/min) ABS preform – right

On the plasma-treated sample, the oxygen and nitrogen intensities increased, and the carbon intensity decreased compared to the untreated sample, which gave reason for further investigation (5. Table).

	Primary composition (%)			O/C rate (%)
	C	O	N	
untreated ABS	94.1	2	3.9	2
plasma treated ABS	79	15.5	5.5	20

5. Table The ratio of carbon, oxygen and nitrogen on the surface of untreated and plasma-treated preforms

We further investigated the narrow environment of the peaks visible in the overview spectrum with a small step width and high resolution. We determined the chemical bonding states of the C and N atoms by curve fitting of the high-resolution C-1s and N-1s photoelectron peaks. On the surface of the untreated ABS sample, there is only one N-1s chemical bonding state at 399.8 eV, which corresponds to the R-CN bond. In the case of the plasma-treated sample, an additional peak appears around 402 eV, which corresponds to the NH_4^+ bond. In the case of the untreated ABS sheet, two peaks can be fitted to the C-1s peak at 285 eV and 286.5 eV, which correspond to the C-H/C-C bonds and the C-OH/R-CN bonds, respectively. The R-CN bond corresponds to 286.3 eV, but cannot be separated from the C-OH by deconvolution. In the case of plasma-treated ABS sheets, a third chemical bonding state can be identified in addition to the C-1s photoelectron peaks corresponding to 285 eV and 286.5 eV at 289 eV, which corresponds to the R-O-C=O and C-O-H chemical bonds (6. Table).

Bonding condition distribution (%)	N1s		C1s		
	R-CN	NH_4^+	C-H / C-C	R-CN / C_O-H	R-O-C / N-CO
untreated ABS	100	0	84.8	15.2	0
plasma treated ABS	82.7	17.7	56.8	31.9	11.3

6. Table Distribution of bond states in the case of nitrogen and carbon atoms

ABS and PA6 are incompatible materials due to their different physical and chemical properties. Neither strong bonds (e.g., H-bonds) nor weaker secondary bonds are likely to form between the two materials due to their polarity-based incompatibility. Based on XPS studies, the plasma likely oxidizes the unsaturations and nitrile groups of ABS, as these are the most reactive groups in ABS. One possible mechanism for the chemical reactions induced by plasma treatment is illustrated in 29. Figure. Plasma treatment can also enable radical or even mixed-mechanism reactions, so the presented reaction

pathway is just one possible solution. I treated plasma treatment formally as OH addition. Molecular rearrangements can occur in the form of proton exchange due to the presence of moisture in the plasma or environment.

29. Figure One of the possible mechanisms of the chemical transformation of the ABS preform surface as a result of plasma treatment. New functional groups detected by XPS studies are marked in red

The formation of dipole-based interactions is also limited in this case due to the presence of apolar aromatic units. The conversion of nitrile groups to amide and carboxylate groups, along with the incoming hydroxyl groups, significantly increases the possibility of H-bond formation. These structural modifications allow for the formation of up to 9 chemically different H-bonds between ABS and PA6 (30. Figure). As a result, a significant bonding force can be created between the originally incompatible ABS preform and the PA6 rib injection-molded onto it as a result of plasma treatment.

30. Figure The possible H-bonds between surface-modified ABS and untreated PA6 (H-bonds do not indicate the exact interactions, but schematically show the bonding possibilities based on the number of donor and acceptor groups of the repeating units)

3. Calculating the bonding strength of overmolded parts

3.1. Development and validation of the novel calculation method of bonding strength

3.1.1. Numerical modelling of overmolding

The temperature at the interface is crucial for calculating bonding strength. To the best of our knowledge, no previous studies have considered the 2D temperature distribution at the interface; instead, all existing research has focused on the 1D temperature distribution at the interface of coupled materials [10, 11]. This study is novel because it combines analytical and numerical approaches to estimate bonding strength, considering the spatial and temporal variations in temperature distribution at the interface. We obtained the temperature field history from Moldflow simulations (Moldflow Insight 2019, Autodesk Inc.) and developed a 3D model of the specimen and a simplified mold with cooling channels (31. Figure).

31. Figure The FEM model with 3D tetrahedral elements, the grey part is the injection mold, cooling channels are marked with dark blue, light blue color was used to mark the part: 1- sprue, 2 – rib, 3 – interface, 4 – base plate, 5 cooling channels

We meshed the model using tetrahedral elements. The average mesh size was 1.2 mm for the specimen components, while in the contact surface area and its surroundings, the mesh size was reduced to 0.3 mm to enhance simulation accuracy.

For the mold, a structured mesh was employed. In the region where the part contacts the mold, we used the same mesh size as for the part; further away, a larger mesh element size was used. In the cooling channel regions, the mesh was refined to improve the accuracy of heat transfer calculations. The mesh for the mold and cooling channels consisted of 2.7 million elements, while the part had 2.5 million elements. For the contact surface, we used a detailed mesh—there were 4750 nodes on the base plate and an equal number of identically positioned nodes on the rib.

The simulations were conducted with the same process parameters as those used during manufacturing. For instance, the initial mold temperature was set to 40 °C or 80 °C. To model cooling, we used a transient cooling mode, allowing the mold temperature to change during cycles. We accounted for the part ejection time and the time required to insert the base plate by setting the "open

mold time" to 5 seconds in the simulation. After 5 seconds, the mold closed, and the base plate remained in the mold for 20 seconds before injection began, allowing the base plate to reach the mold's temperature. The injection molding sequence closely replicated real-life conditions, with a flow rate of $40 \text{ cm}^3/\text{s}$ during the injection phase, followed by a holding phase at 75 MPa for 2 seconds. The combined time for filling, holding, and cooling was set to 25 seconds. The simulation provided the temperature distribution along the interface over time for both the base plate and the rib (32. Figure). In injection overmolding, the temperature history at the interface varies for each node. Therefore, we exported the temperature history data for each node from the simulation results (33. Figure).

32. Figure Temperature distribution at different times on the contact surface of the rib and the base plate side

33. Figure The components and the interface with the nodes ($T_n(t)$ – the temperature of an arbitrary node as a function of time, $T(x,y)$ – the temperature distribution along a certain cross-section at a particular moment

3.1.2. Calculation of temperature history

The original models of bonding strength [21-24] assume uniform temperature across both components and the entire contact surface. However, during overmolding, the surfaces exhibit slight temperature differences due to imperfect heat transfer between the components, resulting in an uneven temperature distribution along the interface. Consequently, these models [21-24] cannot accurately predict the bonding strength of the interface between the substrate and the overmolded rib:

$$D_h = \frac{\sigma}{\sigma_\infty} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Model 1} \quad D_h = \frac{\sigma}{\sigma_\infty} = \left(\frac{l}{L}\right)^{1/2} \left[\sum_{i=0}^n \frac{t_{i+1}^{1/2} - t_i^{1/2}}{t_{rep}(T)^{1/2}} \right]^{1/2}, \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Model 2} \quad D_h = \frac{\sigma}{\sigma_\infty} = \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{t_{i+1}^{1/4} - t_i^{1/4}}{t_{rep}(T)^{1/4}}, \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Model 3} \quad D_h = \frac{\sigma}{\sigma_\infty} = \left[\int_0^t \frac{d\tau}{2\sqrt{\tau} \cdot t_{rep}(\tau)} dt \right]^{1/2}, \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Model 4} \quad D_h = \frac{\sigma}{\sigma_\infty} = \left[\int_0^t \frac{dt}{t_w(T)} dt \right]^{1/4}, \quad (10)$$

where D_h is the degree of healing, σ is the actual bonding strength, σ_∞ is the maximum bonding strength (tensile strength of single-piece specimens), L is length of chain, l is the end of the molecule chain, t_i is the time in the current time step, and t_{rep} is the reptation time at the current, τ is the time interval, t_w is the welding time.

The interface was modeled as described previously, with coincident nodes on the base plate and the rib. The temperature histories of these coincident nodes differ. Therefore, we determined the average temperature of these node pairs, denoted as $T_{node}(t)$. Calculations were performed only in regions where both temperatures exceeded T_g (34. Figure). Upon contact, the overmolded polymer melt initially reaches a maximum temperature and then rapidly cools until it approaches the average interface temperature. Conversely, the temperature of the base plate rises until it similarly nears the average interface temperature.

34. Figure Typical temperature history of a pair of nodes on the rib and plate interface

3.1.3. Calculation of bonding strength

To accurately calculate bonding strength, it is essential to determine the reptation time at given temperatures. The reptation time can be approximated based on work of Wool et al. [3]. It is derived from viscosity measurements, as the relaxation time of the polymer at a specific temperature. The relaxation time is defined as the time required for the elastic modulus (G') of the polymer to equal its storage modulus (G''). We derived the relaxation time of ABS GP-35 at various temperatures from viscosity curves obtained through frequency sweep tests using a parallel plate rotational rheometer (AR2000, TA Instruments, United States). The reptation time of ABS was measured at six different temperatures (150, 170, 190, 210, 230, and 250 °C) at frequencies from 0.01 to 600 rad/s. This test

identified the angular frequency at which G' equals G'' (35. Figure). At a reference temperature of 170 °C, the coefficient of variation across repeated tests did not exceed 4%, with each test conducted five times.

35. Figure Relaxation time obtained by frequency sweep test

Above the glass transition temperature (T_g), the reptation time was determined as a function of temperature, which is crucial for calculating bonding strength. We applied the Williams-Landel-Ferry (WLF) equation (Eq. 4 and 5) to the measured reptation time values, obtaining a continuous function (36. Figure).

36. Figure Fitted WLF curve on the calculated reptation times

$$\log a_T(T) = \log \frac{t_{rep}(T)}{t_{rep}(T_{ref})} \quad (11)$$

where $a_T(T)$ is the shift factor, $t_{rep}(T)$ is the reptation time at temperature T , T_{ref} is the reference temperature.

We used 210 °C as the reference temperature, located in the middle of the tested range, yielding a calculated reptation time of 0.4635 s. Below T_g , the reptation time is considered infinite, creating a vertical asymptote in the WLF equation graph, which depends on C_2 .

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow T_{ref} - C_2} \left(\log \frac{t_{rep}}{t_{rep}(T_{ref})} \right) \rightarrow \infty \quad (12)$$

Thus, at $T=T_{ref}-C_2$, $t_{rep}(T)=\infty$. From this, C_2 was determined:

$$C_2 = T_{ref} - T_g = 210 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} - 103 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} = 107 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \quad (13)$$

We calculated C_1 by averaging its values at each measured point resulting in $C_1=2.33$.

Using the WLF equation, the reptation time (37. Figure) was computed for each node pair from $T_{node}(t)$. When $T_{node}(t)$ falls below T_g , diffusion does not occur, and local bonding strength does not increase between the nodes.

37. Figure Reptation time as a function of time for an individual pair of nodes

We determined the degree of healing using four mathematical models from the literature. Models 1 and 2 use discrete time intervals for reptation time, while Models 3 and 4 utilize continuous functions. The degree of healing (D_h) can be calculated at each node, representing the ratio of evolved bonding strength to the maximum possible, thus $0 \leq D_h \leq 1$. To compare modeling and experimental results, we calculated D_h for the entire contact surface using literature equations for each set of process parameters, such as different mold and melt temperatures. The calculations for all four models involved:

- Determining D_{hi} for each node pair (where i is the node pair number in the mesh).
- Calculating the overall average D_{hav} for the entire contact surface by averaging individual values.

We established the theoretical minimum and maximum boundaries for the degree of healing (D_{hmin} , D_{hmax}) by selecting the minimum and maximum values, unless any nodes remained below T_g throughout the cycle, setting D_{hmin} to zero (38. Figure).

38. Figure The minimum, maximum and average degree of healing calculated with Yang's model at a mold temperature of a) 40 °C and b) 80 °C as a function of melt temperature.

Mesh distribution impacts the accuracy of D_{hav} calculations. Using an even mesh distribution ensures precise calculations with the described method. Model 4 was chosen to present D_h results. Bonding strength was calculated using all four models and compared with measured strength:

$$\sigma_{calc} = \sigma_{\infty} \cdot D_{hav} \quad (14)$$

where σ_{calc} is the calculated bonding strength, σ_{∞} is the maximum bonding strength (tensile strength of single-piece specimens) and D_{hav} is the average degree of healing calculated with the selected model.

3.1.4. Validation of the calculated bonding strength

The base plates were manufactured separately using conventional injection molding, with a melt temperature of 260 °C and a mold temperature of 60 °C. During the overmolding phase, the melt temperatures were varied at 220 °C, 240 °C, 260 °C, 280 °C, and 300 °C, while the mold temperatures were set at 40 °C and 80 °C. Bonding strength was tested with ten samples for each set of parameters. Single-piece specimens were manufactured for each combination of mold and melt temperatures, resulting in consistent tensile strengths. The average tensile strength, 33.7 MPa, was used as the maximum bonding strength (σ_{∞}).

After calculating bonding strength (Eq. 6) using each model (Eq. 7-10), we validated these results against the measured bonding strengths (39. Figure). Three of the four analytical models produced bonding strength values in good agreement with the experimental data. Model 1 exhibited the best correlation with an error of 7%, while Models 3 and 4 showed errors of 11.0% and 11.2%, respectively. Model 2, however, showed significantly worse results, with an error exceeding 200%, contrary to the findings of Bastien and Gillespie [21].

39. Figure Experimental and calculated overall bonding strength with a mold temperature of a) 40 °C and b) 80 °C. Maximum stands for the strength of the single-piece specimens and Experimental data are the measured bonding strengths

We observed that bonding strength increases with both melt and mold temperatures, displaying a saturation curve as a function of melt temperature. Different mold temperatures shift these curves, presenting distinct segments of the saturation curve, as seen in 39. Figure.

We extended our calculation method to other amorphous polymers, specifically polycarbonate (PC) and polystyrene (PS). Melt temperatures were chosen based on the polymers' datasheets. Using Model 4 for our calculations, the results aligned well with the measured bonding strengths (40. Figure). This strong agreement between simulation and experimental results confirms the validity of our proposed simulation method, demonstrating that it can be effectively applied to a range of amorphous polymers where bonding is temperature dependent. Consequently, this calculation method warrants implementation in numerical simulation software, although further modifications are needed to enhance its accuracy.

40. Figure Comparison of measured and calculated bonding strength for PC and PS

3.1.5. Conclusion

We developed a novel calculation method to predict the bonding strength between a base plate and an overmolded element. This method uniquely combines analytical and numerical approaches to estimate bonding strength while accounting for the spatial and temporal unevenness of the temperature distribution at the interface. We simulated the overmolding process to obtain the temperature history of the contact surface and utilized four mathematical models to calculate the degree of healing. The modeling results were verified through mechanical testing of injection overmolded samples. We validated the simulation results using two different mold temperatures and

five different melt temperatures. The results obtained with the proposed simulation method showed good agreement with the test results, with a prediction error of only 7%.

For ABS, the maximum bonding strength between an overmolded element and a substrate was found to be 25 MPa, compared to the theoretical maximum bonding strength of 33.7 MPa. Additionally, we observed that the bonding strength of overmolded specimens increased with both melt temperature and mold temperature.

3.2. Improving the bonding strength calculation method

After the initial method development, we combined then numerical modeling with the numerical modeling of tensile testing. We further enhanced our calculation model by adding different calculation methods, e.g. calculating bonding strength based on nodal and element data.

First, we fitted the WLF equation (Eq. 4-5) on the measured rheological values. With this fitted equation, we calculated the reptation time at every temperature, not only at discrete values. Fitting yielded 6.22 for C_1 and 99.46 for C_2 at the reference temperature of 150 °C with a reference reptation time of 15.95 s.

3.2.1. Numerical modeling of injection overmolding

Traditionally, bonding strength calculations neglect the 2D temperature distribution within the interface, focusing only on 1D variations. Our work addresses this gap by combining analytical and numerical methods to estimate bonding strength while considering temperature's spatial and temporal unevenness across the interface.

We built a detailed 3D model incorporating the specimen, mold, and cooling channels. A refined mesh with element sizes of 0.3 mm was used near the contact surface to capture the temperature variations accurately, while coarser elements were employed in less critical areas. This optimized meshing strategy balanced accuracy with computational efficiency.

Moldex3D software was used for the simulation process. We replicated real-world manufacturing parameters, including initial mold temperature, cooling method, cycle times, and injection parameters. This ensured the simulation accurately reflected the actual bonding process. The simulation yielded a comprehensive dataset of temperature distributions across the interface for each node at various time steps. This data, exported in .a3mc format, served as the foundation for further analysis in Matlab.

3.2.2. Modeling of tensile test

For the simulation of the tensile test, we used Matlab R2021b. As input data for Matlab, we used the temperature history data obtained during the numerical modeling of overmolding. However, the raw data of a simulation is in the .m3c format, which Matlab cannot directly process. Therefore, data from Moldex had to be transformed. 41. Figure/a shows these transformations. First, the .m3c files are converted to a format that Matlab can interpret, the .txt format. The .txt file contains the temperature for each individual node at a certain timestep. The time steps in the .txt file are not quantitative values but just serial numbers in chronological order. To identify the temperature history of the nodes, we must export the time values of each step into a .csv file. Another simulation run is required to identify the nodes that belong to the contact surface. In this simulation run, virtual constraints are placed on the nodes of the contact surface. The data of these nodes are saved in the .sbc format. A .sbc file contains the identifiers of the constrained nodes and allows matching temperature histories with the nodes. We then load the .sbc file into Matlab and isolate these nodes from the simulation. The coordinates of the nodes are also required. For this, the mesh of the model must be in a processable form. In Moldex3D, there is an export option that saves the mesh in the file format .ans, which Matlab can read. This way, data obtained from Moldex3D with Matlab is processed with the use of four different data sources.

41. Figure Data transformation (schematically): (a) the creation of the data matrix needed for the calculations of the degree of healing; (b) transformation of files

3.2.3. Calculations

In Finite Element Method (FEM) modeling, every component is constructed from elements and nodes (42. Figure). Both elements and nodes can be utilized to calculate the bonding strength between a substrate and an overmolded rib. However, the accuracy of this calculation is influenced by the choice of geometric elements. In this study, we demonstrate how nodes and triangular elements can be

employed in the calculation of bonding strength and how the total surface strength can be derived from these elements.

42. Figure The usual structure of the meshed surface and the notation of elements and nodes

From modeling, we obtain the strength distribution through all the individual elements or nodes of the contact surface. In most cases, the strength distribution obtained for individual elements and nodes must be converted into the bonding strength of the whole contact surface. We have developed a new, more precise method to model a tensile test. Using the measurements and simulation results, we calculated the bonding strength of a contact surface with four different methods (43. Figure).

43. Figure The methods we developed for the calculation of the bonding strength

We calculated the bonding strength of the interface by averaging the bonding strength of all the individual nodes ("Method 1"). Then, by using the bonding strength of individual nodes, we modeled the tensile test and determined the overall bonding strength of the interface ("Method 3"). Method 2 is similar to Method 1, and Method 4 to Method 3; the only difference is that we used the bonding strength of the individual elements for the calculations in Methods 2 and 4.

3.2.3.1. Calculation of the degree of healing in nodes

The bonding strength of each node can be calculated using the healing equation developed by Yang and Pitchumani [24]. We employ reptation time to determine the degree of healing, a method proven effective for this calculation in the previous chapter. To utilize reptation time, it is essential to know the temperature history at each node $T_i(t)$ and the temperature-dependent reptation time of the material $t_{rep}(T)$:

$$D_{h,i} = \frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{\infty}} = \left[\int_0^t \frac{1}{t_{rep}(T_i(t))} dt \right]^{1/4}, \quad (15)$$

For the calculation of healing, the reptation time curve from the start to the end of the process must be integrated. This curve (44. Figure/a) can be derived from the temperature history obtained from injection molding simulations (44. Figure/b) (Chapter 3.2.1 Numerical modeling of injection overmolding) and the measured temperature-dependent reptation time of the material using the transformed WLF equation (44. Figure/c) (Chapter 1.14):

$$t_{rep}(T) = 10^{\frac{C_1(T-T_{ref})}{C_2+(T+T_{ref})}} \cdot t_{ref,rep} \quad (16)$$

Due to the nature of injection molding simulations, results are obtained in discrete time steps. At each time step, each node has a discrete temperature value corresponding to the reptation time of the material at that temperature. Integration can be performed either through curve fitting or numerical integration of the points. The degree of healing results can be plotted to identify weak points on the healing surface (45. Figure). 45. Figure demonstrates that the degree of healing is lowest at the edges of the cross-section. These results are consistent with those reported in the work of Akkerman et al. [26].

44. Figure The calculated (a) reptation time history of a node or surface element from (b) the temperature history and from (c) the temperature-dependent reptation time curve.

45. Figure Representation of the degrees of healing (DoH) on the welded surface calculated from nodal temperature values.

3.2.3.2. Calculation of the degree of healing in the elements which belong to the contact surface

The surface area associated with each node can vary, even if the elements are of the same size. This variation occurs because the surface area of a node adjacent to the wall is smaller than that of a node in the central part of the cross-section. Furthermore, the surface area for nodes in the corners is even smaller (46. Figure). Generally, the temperature is lowest near the mold wall, leading to weaker healing in those regions (45. Figure). Therefore, assuming the same surface area for all nodes would underestimate the strength of the entire interface. This error can be mitigated by calculating the tensile test using the elements on the surface rather than the nodes, which requires some modifications compared to node-based calculations.

46. Figure The area which belongs to a node in the middle of the contact surface (blue), the node next to the wall (yellow), and the node in the corner (orange).

Temperature history data are derived from injection molding simulation results for each node. Using the temperature history of the nodes connected to the elements, we calculated the temperature history for individual elements. At each time step, the temperature of an element is the average of the temperatures of the nodes connected to that element at that time step (Eq. 17):

$$T_{ek}(t_i) = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m T_{nk_j}(t_i)}{m}, \quad (17)$$

where $T_{ek}(t_i)$ is the temperature of the k^{th} element in timestep t_i , m is the number of elements connected to the k^{th} element, $T_{nk_j}(t_i)$ is the temperature of the j^{th} node at timestep t_i , which is connected to the k^{th} element (47. Figure).

47. Figure The area of calculated bonding strength and the notation of the temperature of nodes and elements.

We obtained the distribution of the degree of healing on the contact surface from the temperature history of the contact surface with the healing calculation equations used in the previous chapter (Chapter 3.2.3.1 Calculation of the degree of healing in nodes) (48. Figure).

48. Figure Representation of degree of healing on the contact surface

3.2.3.3. The calculation of bonding strength from the degree of healing

From the degree of healing, the bonding strength at a specific point can be calculated using the "infinite" bond strength. This value represents the strength that would be achieved if the bonding time were infinitely long. When the material has an infinite time to bond, the properties at the bond locations are equivalent to those of the bulk material. Therefore, the tensile strength of the material can be used as the "infinite" bonding strength, as described in Equations (18) and (19). To measure the tensile strength of the material, a "single-piece" specimen was produced, and tensile tests were conducted on it.

$$\sigma_{n,j} = D_{h_{n,j}} \cdot \sigma_{\infty}, \quad (18)$$

where $\sigma_{n,j}$ is the bonding strength of the j^{th} node, $D_{h_{n,j}}$ is the degree of healing of the j^{th} node and σ_{∞} is the tensile strength of the material.

$$\sigma_{e,k} = D_{h_{e,k}} \cdot \sigma_{\infty}, \quad (19)$$

where $\sigma_{e,j}$ is the bonding strength of the j^{th} element, $D_{h_{e,j}}$ is the degree of healing of the j^{th} element and σ_{∞} is the tensile strength of the material.

3.2.3.4. Total bonding strength calculated by averaging

The calculation methods discussed in Sections 3.2.3 provide the bonding strength distribution across the contact surface. In studies focusing on bonding strength calculation, averaging is often employed.

For instance, Giusti and Lucchetta [9] averaged the contact surface temperature, while Akkerman et al. [26] averaged the degree of healing. In both cases, the bonding strength of the interface was calculated using average values of either the interface temperature or the degree of healing. However, these assumptions typically lead to an overestimation of bonding strength, resulting in a discrepancy between modeled and experimental results exceeding 10%.

In our current research, we first obtained the bonding strength distribution by analyzing individual nodes and elements. We then calculated the bonding strength of the interface by averaging the bonding strengths of the nodes (Eq. 18) and the surface elements (Eq. 19).

$$\sigma_{t,n} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^i \sigma_j}{i} \quad (20)$$

where $\sigma_{t,n}$ is the bonding strength of the total surface calculated from nodal bonding strengths, σ_j is the bonding strength of the j^{th} node and i is the number of nodes on the welded surface.

Averaging bonding strengths is not physically accurate for calculating total bonding strength. Additionally, calculating the average bonding strength from nodes introduces errors, as it does not account for the non-uniform distribution of nodes across the contact surface. To correct this error, we used the bonding strength of the surface elements, where strength values are weighted by the surface area. To calculate the weighted average bonding strength, the area of the surface elements must be known. This area can be calculated from the coordinates of the elements, which can be exported from any simulation or meshing software. For triangular elements, the area of the triangle can be calculated from the coordinates as follows. Coordinates of nodes connected to the element:

$$P_{nk,1} (a_1, a_2, a_3), P_{nk,2} (b_1, b_2, b_3), P_{nk,3} (c_1, c_2, c_3) \quad (21)$$

The area of the triangle is:

$$A_{e_k} = \frac{|u|}{2} \quad (22)$$

Where u is:

$$u = \overrightarrow{P_{nk,1} P_{nk,2}} \times \overrightarrow{P_{nk,1} P_{nk,3}} \quad (23)$$

where $P_{nk,j}$ is the coordinate vector of j^{th} a node connected to the element, and A_{e_k} is the area of the k^{th} element.

$$\sigma_{t,e} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^z \sigma_k * A_k}{A_{total}}, \quad (24)$$

where $\sigma_{t,e}$ is the bonding strength of the total surface calculated from the bonding strength of the elements, σ_k is the bonding strength of the k^{th} element, z is the number of elements on the welded surface, A_k is the area of the k^{th} element and A_{total} is the area of the whole welded surface.

3.2.3.5. Modeling the tensile test

By modeling a tensile test, we can simulate the breaking process of the material. This can be done by considering the bonding strength at nodes and within elements. The key difference between these two approaches is that, for nodes, the associated surface area is not explicitly considered. It is assumed that each node corresponds to an equal portion of the surface area, and the bonding strength of these portions (49. Figure) is equivalent to the bonding strength at the node. This assumption is correct if the mesh elements on the contacting surface are of approximately equal size.

49. Figure The surface area of an individual node (blue area) when we use the bonding strength of the nodes to calculate the bonding strength of the whole surface.

When modeling tensile testing, our objective is to determine the maximum force the specimen can withstand before breaking. We simplify the problem by assuming that the force applied at each point on the surface is uniform, resulting in a uniform stress distribution. As the applied force increases, the stress at the surface increases. At points where the stress exceeds the local bonding strength, those portions of the surface break. Consequently, the undamaged surface area decreases, causing the stress in the remaining intact parts of the surface to increase. The force continues to increase until the entire contact surface breaks. The maximum tensile force (F_{max}) at the last timestep, when the entire surface has failed, is used for calculations. The engineering (σ_{total}) strength can be calculated from this force (F_{max}) and the initial area of the surface (A) using Eq. 25:

$$\sigma_{total} = \frac{F_{max}}{A} \quad (25)$$

To model tensile testing with surface elements, we need to know both the bonding strength within the elements and their sizes. Similar to the node-based calculation, we assume the applied force is uniform across the surface, resulting in equal stress on all elements. When the stress in an element exceeds its bonding strength, the surface begins to break, reducing the total surface area by the area of the failed element. Thus, the load-bearing contact surface area progressively decreases, and the undamaged elements experience increasing stress. The tensile force increases until the entire contact surface fails, and the resulting maximum force is used to calculate the overall bonding strength of the surface.

3.2.4. Modeling example

To illustrate the modeling of the tensile test, we consider a contact surface comprising 3 by 3 square surface elements, each with an area of 1 mm², resulting in a total surface area of 9 mm². Assume the calculated bonding strengths are as shown in 50. Figure.

50. Figure Sample surface to illustrate tensile test modeling, where the number written in the surface element indicates the strength of the surface element in MPa.

We first examined the total strength of the interface obtained by averaging the bonding strengths. The surface consists of nine elements (51. Figure/a). The strengths of these elements were averaged, yielding a total surface tensile strength of 1.78 MPa (Eq. 26).

$$\sigma_{total} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_{Ni}}{n} = \frac{16}{9} = 1.78 \text{ MPa} \tag{26}$$

For tensile test modeling, as the force on the surface increases and the calculated stress exceeds the bonding strength of a surface portion, that portion will fail. The first surface element fails at 9 N (51. Figure/b) since, at this moment, the tensile stress is 1 MPa on each surface element. Increasing the tensile force to 10 N results in a stress of 2 MPa for the five remaining elements, causing four more elements to fail (51. Figure/c). Consequently, the last undamaged surface element will experience a stress of 10 MPa and will also fail (51. Figure/d). The surface can thus withstand a force of 10 N, divided by the initial cross-section, resulting in a total surface strength of 1.11 MPa.

This demonstration shows that, using this more realistic calculation method, the tensile strength that the interface of bonded parts can withstand is reduced by 60%.

51. Figure The process of modeling the tensile test, (a) the initial, completely intact (white) surface, (b) surface portions that are broken by 9 N (grey), (c) surface portions that are broken by 10 N and (d) the entire surface that is broken by 10 N due to the reduced cross-section.

3.2.5. Results and validation of methods

This section focuses on validating the modeling methods for predicting the bonding strength of overmolded specimens (52. Figure).

Calculation method / Element used	Averaging	Tensile test modeling
Node	Method 1	Method 3
Surface element	Method 2	Method 4

52. Figure Methods of the modeling of bonding strength in an overmolded specimen

Mesh parameters can significantly influence calculation results. To examine this effect, we created various meshes with different element sizes (53. Figure).

53. Figure Contact surface meshes with different parameters of the mesh (For a better visibility, only a tiny section of the meshed part is shown)

Following simulations in Moldex3D, we calculated the strength of individual elements and nodes using temperature histories and node coordinates in MATLAB. The strength distributions across the nodes and elements of the contact surface were plotted, highlighting weak points on the contact surface. Analyzing the degree of healing map from nodes (54. Figure/a) is challenging as it does not provide a continuous surface picture, displaying only the degree of healing at each node. Conversely, the degree of healing map plotted with elements offers better analysis (54. Figure/b). As the element size decreases, the calculated degree of healing distribution becomes increasingly detailed and accurate (54. Figure).

54. Figure The plot of the degree of healing calculated with (a) nodes and with (b) surface elements.

3.2.5.1. Validation of method 1 and method 2

The strength of the entire contact surface was determined by averaging the strength of the elements (Method 2) and the nodes (Method 1). The simplest approach to obtain the bonding strength of the entire surface is to average the bonding strengths calculated for individual nodes (48. Figure, Method 1). Another approach involves calculating the strengths of the surface elements and then averaging them, weighted by their area, to yield the bonding strength of the total surface (48. Figure, Method 2).

We aim to highlight the significant error introduced by averaging, which often greatly overestimates the actual bonding strength. This overestimation occurs because averaging assigns equal weight to all points and surfaces, whereas, in reality, the less bonded locations primarily determine the overall strength. The results from nodal and surface element calculations are similar due to the mesh elements on the surface being nearly uniform in size (55. Figure). The difference between the results of nodes and surface elements arises because the nodes adjacent to the wall exhibit the lowest strength. Since nodes lack a surface area, we cannot account for their smaller effective surface, which further reduces the overall bonding strength (Chapter 3.2.3.2 Calculation of the degree of healing in the elements which belong to the contact surface).

55. Figure Total bond strength calculated by averaging the strength in the nodes and elements with uniform element sizes.

When the mesh elements on the surface vary in size, the total surface strength calculated using nodes and elements can differ significantly. While the bonding strength obtained from elements (Method 2)

remains consistent regardless of element size, the strength calculated from nodes (Method 1) is highly dependent on the mesh density (56. Figure).

56. Figure Total bonding strength of a contact surface calculated by averaging the strength in nodes and elements with meshes of unequal element sizes.

This discrepancy occurs because nodes associated with smaller mesh elements are not weighted proportionally less. Therefore, if more elements are present in the warmer regions of the surface, the calculated total bonding strength will be higher than with an evenly spaced mesh. Conversely, if more elements are in the colder regions of the surface, the calculated strength will be lower (57. Figure).

57. Figure (a) The temperature of the contact surface and the mesh (b) when there are more elements at the warmer places and (c) when there are more elements at the colder places.

3.2.5.2. Validation of method 3 and method 4

In Methods 3 and 4, we modeled the tensile test to determine the bonding strength of the entire contact surface, using nodal strength for Method 3 and surface element strength for Method 4. The bonding strengths obtained by Methods 3 and 4 are significantly more accurate than those provided by Methods 1 and 2 (58. Figure). This increased accuracy arises from the ability of Methods 3 and 4 to

track the breakage process, a capability not afforded by the averaging approaches of Methods 1 and 2. The results obtained from nodal and element-based calculations are very similar because the element sizes at the contact surface were nearly identical, rendering the size-based weighting of surface elements insignificant.

58. Figure Total bonding strength of the contact surface defined by Methods 1–4 for different numbers of mesh elements

When utilizing nodal-based methods (Method 1 and Method 3), we observed lower bonding strength values compared to element-based methods (Method 2 and Method 4). This discrepancy is due to the smaller specific area of nodes adjacent to the mold wall compared to those at the center of the contact surface (46. Figure). This phenomenon, unaccounted for in Methods 1 and 3, results in a reduced calculated tensile strength for the entire contact surface near the mold wall where the temperature is lower (58. Figure).

However, when surface elements are of varying sizes, nodal-based strength calculations lose accuracy, even with tensile test modeling (59. Figure). In such cases, total tensile strength should be derived from the surface elements, as this method provides the most precise approximation of bonding strength.

59. Figure Total bonding strength obtained by tensile test modeling in the case of an unequally spaced mesh

Our findings demonstrate that Method 3 is sensitive to the size of the elements on the contact surface. When element sizes vary, nodal strength calculations should be avoided due to the lack of weighting. Under these conditions, bonding strength should be calculated through tensile modeling using the strength of the interface elements to achieve the most accurate results (60. Figure).

60. Figure Calculation method results for bonding strength with the measurement results (blue bar - results obtained by tensile test modeling, yellow bar – results obtained by averaging)

3.2.5.3. Validation with other materials

Given the considerable variation in the healing behavior of different amorphous materials, we also tested our calculation method with polystyrene (Versalis Edistir N 3910) (61. Figure/a) and polycarbonate (Covestro Makrolon 2205) (61. Figure/b). To achieve this, we manufactured test specimens for validating our modeling results. Additionally, we measured the strength of a "single-piece" specimen for each material to serve as the maximum strength in our calculations. Since melt temperature significantly influences weld strength, we prepared specimens with a range of melt temperatures. Broad melt temperature ranges were selected for all materials. In most cases, the calculated bonding strength fell within the standard deviation of the measured results, providing a good approximation within the examined range.

61. Figure Calculated and measured bonding strength of a) PS (Versalis Edistir N 3910) b) PC (Covestro Makrolon 2205).

3.2.6. Conclusion

We have developed a universal modeling method that accurately predicts the bonding strength of the interface formed during overmolding. Through the simulation of tensile tests, we demonstrated that our method can predict the bonding strength of the interface in overmolded parts with significantly higher accuracy compared to the widely used averaging method. The bonding strength predicted by

our model deviates from the measured results by less than 1%, whereas the difference is typically 10% or more with the averaging approach.

Our method integrates the analytical modeling of reptation, numerical modeling of the overmolding process, and tensile test simulations. The unique features of our proposed method are:

- It accounts for the uneven temperature distribution on the contact surface during overmolding.
- It includes tensile test modeling, which provides a more realistic representation of the breaking process than the commonly used averaging method.

3.3. Extend the calculation method to semi-crystalline materials

3.3.1. Results of tensile testing

The bond strength of both polypropylenes exhibited a significant increase with rising melt temperatures. Notably, the homopolymer (H145F) demonstrated lower bond strength under identical conditions (62. Figure/a), despite its higher tensile strength compared to the random copolymer (R959A) (62. Figure/b). These findings suggest that the homopolymer possesses inferior welding properties relative to the tested random copolymer.

62. Figure The measured tensile strength of a) overmolded specimens and b) single-piece specimens

3.3.2. Reptation time of PP and WLF fitting

To calculate the reptation time of the materials, we performed frequency sweep tests with a parallel plate rotational rheometer AR2000 (TA Instruments, New Castle, USA). Measurement for the calculation of reptation time of PP was performed at five temperatures (180, 200, 220, 240, and 260 °C); then the WLF curve was fitted (4-5) to the measured values. Fitting yielded 2.2 and 2.21 for C_1 for H145F and R959A respectively. C_2 was found to be 190 °C at the reference temperature of 170 °C with a reference reptation time of 0.0075 and 0.0023984 s for H145F and R959A respectively.

3.3.3. Numerical calculation of overmolding

The temperature history of the contact surface was determined with the use of the Moldex3D R21 (CoreTech System Co., Taiwan) simulation; the process parameters were the same as in injection overmolding.

3.3.4. Calculation of reptation time and degree of healing of amorphous part

We used the newly developed method to calculate the bonding strength of amorphous polymers (63. Figure). The initial step involves determining the degree of healing (D_h) for all surface elements. The modified Yang formula (Eq. 15) is used to calculate the degree of healing, requiring the reptation time

($t_{rep}(T)$) for each element. This reptation time can be obtained from the simulated temperature history using the WLF equation. Once the degree of healing for each element is known, the bonding strength of each element can be determined using the tensile strength of the material (Eq. 14). For this purpose, we utilized the tensile strength of the injection-molded pieces from our experiments. This method allows us to create a weld distribution map for the overmolded surface based on the calculated bonding strengths. However, for validation, we need the bond strength of the entire surface, which can be measured through a tensile test. The overall bond strength can be determined by modeling the tensile test from the bond strength of the individual elements, a process detailed in Section 3.2 Improving the bonding strength calculation method.

63. Figure Steps of the bonding strength calculation method and the data required for the steps

3.3.5. Differences between the healing of amorphous and semi-crystalline polymers

The method used to calculate the bonding strength of amorphous polymers cannot be directly applied to semi-crystalline polymers due to the significant influence of crystalline particles on the movement of polymer molecules. However, in the melt state, the crystalline regions disintegrate, rendering the material amorphous. Therefore, the calculation method for amorphous polymers can be applied to semi-crystalline materials above their crystalline melting temperature. Initially, the formation of crystalline particles only slightly restricts molecular movement. As the number and size of crystalline particles increase, molecular mobility becomes progressively more restricted until diffusion ceases and the bonding process halts (64. Figure).

64. Figure The bonding of semi-crystalline polymers demonstrated with their DSC curve

Our objective was to account for the effect of crystalline particles using the reptation time curve, thereby adapting the calculation method for amorphous polymers to semi-crystalline polymers. The reptation time curve varies with temperature and can be described using the WLF equation. The macro-Brownian motion of molecular chains in amorphous polymers ceases at the glass transition temperature, preventing healing below this threshold. Consequently, the reptation time at the glass transition temperature is infinite, which is evident from a well-fitted WLF curve (65. Figure).

65. Figure Fitted WLF curve as a function of temperature

Similar to amorphous polymers, the reptation time of semi-crystalline polymers is also infinite at the glass transition temperature. The molecules possess sufficient energy for macro-Brownian motion up to this temperature. To account for the limiting effect of crystallization, we defined a limit temperature at which healing stops. Crystalline particle formation occurs over a range of temperatures rather than at a single temperature. Given the high cooling rates during injection molding (approximately 500–1000 °C/min), the formation of crystalline particles can be considered instantaneous. Thus, we simplified the process by assuming that healing of semi-crystalline polymers stops at a specific temperature, called the limit temperature. At this limit temperature, the healing of the polymer stops, leading to an increase in the modified shift factor and reptation time to infinity (66. Figure).

66. Figure Defined reptation time curve for semi-crystalline polymers

3.3.6. Determining the limit temperature

To determine the limit temperature, we must investigate the crystallization properties of the polymer. Given that the crystallization temperature range of polymers significantly depends on the cooling rate, and cooling rates are high during injection molding, we measured the crystallization temperature range

of the materials at different cooling rates using Flash DSC (67. Figure). The limit temperature was identified for each cooling rate within the crystallization temperature range measured at that specific cooling rate.

67. Figure Flash DSC results of MOL Tipplen H145F in the case of cooling

In the injection molding process, the inserts heat up. Accurate detection of the onset of healing requires establishing a limit temperature curve based on the heating rate. This necessitates determining the crystallization temperature range of the polymer, which we achieved with Flash DSC tests at varying heating rates (68. Figure).

68. Figure Flash DSC results of MOL Tipplen H145F in the case of heating

Using Flash DSC, we identified the start and end of the crystallization temperature range based on the applied cooling and heating rates (69. Figure). Within this temperature range, the limit temperature for healing is determined. Its value can be influenced by various factors such as the crystalline proportion and the type of crystals present.

69. Figure The chosen limit temperature (with blue) and the start and end of the crystallization temperature range as a function of cooling and heating rate for MOL Tipplen H145F

3.3.7. Reptation time curve of semi-crystalline polymers

Once the limit temperature curve for the material has been established, the initial step in the calculation is to determine the reptation time curve. To achieve this, it is necessary to define the limits of healing. The first step involves determining the cooling and heating rates from the modeled temperature history of a specific point on the healing surface. 70. Figure illustrates how the cooling and heating limit temperatures are identified.

70. Figure The limit temperature calculated from the temperature history of an element on a healing surface and the bonding interval

Healing initiates when the temperature of the point exceeds the heating limit temperature and continues until the temperature drops below the cooling limit temperature. Within this interval, the reptation time can be calculated using the fitted WLF equation obtained from the rotational rheometer. Outside this interval, the reptation time is considered infinite as no healing occurs (71. Figure). Using these reptation time curves, the overall surface bonding strength can be calculated with our method (Section 3.2 Improving the bonding strength calculation method.).

71. Figure Example of a reptation time curve of an element with a temperature history shown in 65. Figure for a semi-crystalline polymer (MOL Tipplen H145F) – the curve is similar for other semi-crystalline polymers

3.3.8. Validation of the method using semi-crystalline polymers

This method was validated with two types of PP. We observed that the calculation method provides accurate estimates of the measured bonding strengths when appropriate limit temperatures are selected (72. Figure). The calculated bonding strengths for both materials fall within the standard deviation of the measured bonding strengths, except at the maximum melt temperature for the homopolymer and the minimum melt temperature for the random copolymer. In these instances, the calculated bonding strength overestimates the actual bonding strength.

72. Figure Measured and calculated bonding strength of a) a homopolymer polypropylene (MOL Tipplen H145F) and b) a random copolymer polypropylene (MOL Tipplen R959A)

3.3.9. Conclusion

This chapter details our effective method for calculating bonding strength in semi-crystalline materials. To develop this method, we expanded upon our existing calculation technique designed for amorphous polymers, making necessary adjustments. Our approach involves creating a limit temperature curve, which accurately determines the onset and cessation of the healing process in semi-crystalline polymers. To validate our method, we tested two distinct types of PP: a homopolymer and a random copolymer. Our findings indicate that our calculation method can predict bonding strength with high accuracy, exhibiting an average error rate of under 10%.

4. 3D printing and injection overmolded parts adhesion

The bonding strength between the printed and overmolded parts can be improved by modifying the surface roughness because 'rough' surfaces have a greater area for bonding. Another method is to create protruding ridges or deeply pitted surface, which will have a larger contact area. Therefore, the mechanical force for pulling out the overmolded parts from these pits or ridges lead to a substantial increase in the work of debonding. If the overmolded material thoroughly penetrates the pits or surround the ridges, it may not be possible to pull out the ribs without fracturing them.

4.1. Overmolding and overprinting with ABS

In this section, we examined five different ways to further improve the bonding strength between 3D-printed and overmolded elements. The first method increases bonding strength by increasing the surface roughness of the 3D-printed baseplate — this was achieved by optimizing FFF processing parameters. We varied the printing speed (20, 40, 60, and 80 mm/sec), the height of a layer (0.1 and 0.2 mm), and printing orientation (0/90 and +45/-45 deg). The second method of increasing bonding strength is creating a so-called "infill", which is practically a grid-like structure. We examined infill densities in the range of 50 to 100%. The third method is creating a "local infill density", where a triangular pattern of reduced density is made only in the contact area of the baseplate and the overmolded rib. The width of the contact area was 2 mm; the examined infill densities ranged from 0 to 100% with a step of 25%. The fourth method we investigated was mechanical interlocking. We addressed six types of mechanical interlocking patterns (73. Figure). The fifth method was introducing fiber reinforcement in the contact area and the ribs. We created three different combinations: reinforced preform/unreinforced ribs, unreinforced preform/reinforced ribs, and reinforced preform/reinforced ribs. The constant and variable parameters for each method are presented in 7. Table.

73. Figure Methods of bonding strength improvement, which involve modifying the base plate

Method	Varied parameters	Constant parameters
Printing parameters	Printing speed (20, 40, 60, 80 mm/s) Layer height (0.1, 0.2 mm) Printing orientation (0/90, 45/-45)	Infill density – 100% Infill pattern – Rectilinear lines Nozzle temperature – 250 °C Platform temperature – 105 °C
Infill density	Infill density (100, 95, 90, 80, 75, 50 %)	Infill pattern – Rectilinear lines Nozzle temperature – 250 °C Platform temperature – 105 °C Infill printing speed – 40 mm/s Layer height – 0.2 mm Printing orientation – 45/-45
Local infill density	Local infill density (100, 75, 50, 25, 0 %) Local infill pattern – Triangular grid Local infill printing speed – 10 mm/s	Infill density – 100% Infill pattern – Rectilinear lines Nozzle temperature – 250 °C Platform temperature – 105 °C
Mechanical Interlocking	Microstructure type (6 types) Microstructure printing speed – 10 mm/s	Infill printing speed – 40 mm/s Layer height – 0.2 mm
Fibre reinforcement	Reinforcement type (3 types)	Printing orientation – 45/-45

7. Table Constant and varied FFF parameters for all examined methods

4.1.1. Effect of printing parameters and surface roughness on the bonding strength

The study's objective is to analyze the impact of printing parameters on the surface roughness of the FFF printed ABS parts. The surface roughness will, in turn, affect the bonding between the overmolded and the printed parts⁸. Table shows the three different parameters and their levels selected for the study.

Printing parameters	Symbol	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4
Printing speed [mm/s]	v_{print}	20	40	60	80
Layer height [mm]	h_{layer}	0.1		0.2	
Printing orientation [°]	O_{print}	0/90		+45/-45	

8. Table Printing parameters and their levels

The specimens were divided into 16 sets with different combinations of FFF processing parameters: printing speed (v_{print}), layer height (h_{layer}), and printing orientation (O_{print}), as shown in 9. Table⁹. The term 'build time' means the total time from the start of the print to the nozzle's return to the initial position.

The data presented in 9. Table indicates that surface roughness (Ra) is very high compared to traditional manufacturing processes, such as injection molding. In the plastic injection molding industry, a mean Ra value of 0.05 μm is recommended, while our FFF printed samples had Ra ranging from 2.28 to 21.28 μm . The contact-based surface roughness measurement yielded a very high standard deviation

between the Ra values of the same set. This might be because of the difference in the direction the probe was moving (along printing orientation (0°) or 90° to printing orientation). Therefore, we only used laser-based area surface roughness measurement (Sa) for further analysis.

FFF processing parameters				Results						
Set	V _{print} (mm/s)	h _{layer} (mm)	O _{print} (deg)	Ra (μm)		Sa (μm)		Bonding Strength (MPa)		Build time (hours)
				Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
1	20	0.1	0/90	3.35	1.70	36.3	2.16	10.5	1.8	4.71
2	20	0.1	45/-45	7.11	1.79	23.6	5.47	10.2	1.4	4.71
3	40	0.1	0/90	7.66	3.09	35.1	4.54	10.4	1.1	2.64
4	40	0.1	45/-45	9.90	1.92	29.3	3.36	12.9	1.3	2.64
5	60	0.1	0/90	7.96	4.77	33.1	3.09	12.2	1.8	1.91
6	60	0.1	45/-45	9.47	1.25	27.9	3.45	11.7	1.3	1.91
7	80	0.1	0/90	11.06	4.37	34.3	3.73	9.9	1.2	1.50
8	80	0.1	45/-45	11.15	1.44	26.0	6.66	12.1	0.9	1.50
9	20	0.2	0/90	2.28	1.24	87.1	4.93	10.1	1.5	2.49
10	20	0.2	45/-45	21.24	4.02	65.5	7.47	8.9	1.6	2.49
11	40	0.2	0/90	2.38	1.04	78.1	7.12	11.3	0.7	1.49
12	40	0.2	45/-45	20.97	3.85	61.8	3.43	12.4	1.5	1.49
13	60	0.2	0/90	21.28	7.60	22.4	4.13	10.1	1.2	1.17
14	60	0.2	45/-45	15.22	5.18	24.2	6.29	11.6	2.0	1.17
15	80	0.2	0/90	18.61	4.76	21.2	3.04	11.2	3.0	0.99
16	80	0.2	45/-45	20.97	3.44	23.1	7.12	11.5	0.9	0.99

9. Table Design of Experiments for different printing parameters and the results Printing parameters and their levels

At a layer height of 0.1 mm, we found that printing speed does not affect the surface roughness irrespective of printing orientation (74. Figure). This could be because each raster width is very small at 0.1 mm, so the air gap between the raster remains the same in any printing speed. On the other hand, at a layer height of 0.2 mm, it is evident that surface roughness is much higher than in the case of a layer height of 0.1 mm with both printing orientations because of the broad air gap. This is shown in 75. Figure. However, we observed a sudden decrease in surface roughness above a printing speed of 40 mm/s. This phenomenon can be attributed to the way the layers are deposited at lower speeds. At lower speeds (20 and 40 mm/s), the layers are deposited and cooled very slowly, leading to more definite patterns, which leads to higher surface roughness. At higher speeds (60 and 80 mm/s), the deposited filaments were stretched, and the layers were smoothed; thus, surface roughness was lower.

74. Figure Comparison of surface roughness (Sa) at different printing speeds at 0.1 mm (a) and 0.2 mm (b) individual layer thickness

75. Figure FFF printed base plates showing the raster angle, and the raster width for (a) Set1 – 0.1 mm layer thickness (b) Set 9 – 0.2 mm layer thickness

4.1.2. Correlation between surface roughness and bonding strength with Taguchi method

One of the well-established optimization methods is Taguchi’s method, which is adopted in Minitab software by analyzing the predefined design of experiments (DOE). We have used the DOE approach (Taguchi L orthogonal array of L16) by controlling the printing parameters at mixed and different levels. We have initially adopted the Taguchi design because of its ease of data handling and minimum experimental runs. The printing parameters at different mixed levels and their corresponding output values are presented in 7 and 8. The factors that affect output performance are classified into two categories: controllable and noise factors. The noise factors are nothing but factors that are not controlled during the printing process, like environmental temperature, humidity, etc. Here, the signal to noise ratio (S/N ratio) helps obtain an optimal quality design with a minor variation. In the FFF process, the surface roughness (Sa) is the average of the highest peak and the valley of the surface profile. For Sa, the objective is to obtain the more significant values, thus using the S/N ratio (larger is better). This is because larger surface roughness gives a larger surface area for contact with the overmolding melt, hence more significant bonding strength. Similarly, for the bonding strength, obviously, ‘larger the better’ is preferred. The formula for larger is better S/N ratio is as follows:

$$\eta = -10 \log \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{y_i^2}$$

For build time, the objective optimal value is smaller is better. The formula for the S/N ratio is,

$$\eta = -10 \log \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i^2$$

where η is the S/N ratio; y_{we} is the i th result of the experiment; n is the experiment repeats.

We have used Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to evaluate the significance of each factor (printing parameters) to the response (roughness, bonding strength, and build time). This ANOVA analysis uses the p-value to determine the significant FFF parameter that influences the obtained experimental response. By this method, we have used the hypothesis test according to the p-value obtained for each factor. If the p-value is less than the α -value, the higher the probability of rejecting the null hypothesis and see that parameter as a significant one. If the p-value is less than 0.05, then the corresponding parameter is statistically significant with a confidence level of 95%. 10. Table represents the ANOVA results for surface roughness. Printing speed has the most significant effect on surface roughness (44.02%), followed by printing orientation (3.68%) and layer height (3.41%). Thus, higher speed makes the surface smoother.

Meanwhile, the bonding strength was also influenced more by printing speed (41.67%), as shown in 11. Table. The time required to create the preform by FFF is build time. The ANOVA results for build time are shown in 12. Table. Printing speed has the highest effect on build time (66.99%), followed by layer height (32.92%), and printing orientation does not affect build time. It is evident that printing speed affects build time. An increase in layer height reduces the layers required to print the part, therefore reduces nozzle head movement. It is observed that none of the selected parameters shows a significance of 95%; therefore, more rigorous controls are needed to achieve the desired surface roughness and bonding strength.

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-value	P-value	Contribution
PS	3	0.000935	0.000312	3.00	0.082	44.02%
LH	1	0.000072	0.000072	0.70	0.423	3.41%
PO	1	0.000078	0.000078	0.75	0.406	3.68%
Error	10	0.001039	0.000104			48.89%
Total	15	0.002125				100%

10. Table The ANOVA for surface roughness (S_a) (Note that, DF is the Degree of Freedom, Adj. SS – Adjusted Sums of Squares, Adj. MS – Adjusted Mean Squares, F-value -- is the test statistic used to determine whether the term is associated with the response, P-value – is a probability that measures the evidence against the null hypothesis)

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-value	P-value	Contribution
PS	3	3603.4	1201.1	3.22	0.070	41.67%
LH	1	240.9	240.9	0.65	0.440	2.79%
PO	1	1074.5	1074.5	2.88	0.120	12.43%
Error	10	3729.2	372.9			43.12%
Total	15	8648.0				100%

11. Table The ANOVA for bonding strength (Note that, DF is the Degree of Freedom, Adj. SS – Adjusted Sums of Squares, Adj. MS – Adjusted Mean Squares, F-value -- is the test statistic used to determine whether the term is associated with the response, P-value – is a probability that measures the evidence against the null hypothesis)

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-value	P-value	Contribution
PS	3	0.211559	0.070520	2594.56	0.000	66.99%
LH	1	0.103980	0.103980	3825.62	0.000	32.92%
PO	1	0.000000	0.000000	0.00	1.000	0.00%
Error	10	0.000272	0.000027			0.09%
Total	15	0.315810				100%

12. Table The ANOVA for build time (Note that, DF is the Degree of Freedom, Adj. SS – Adjusted Sums of Squares, Adj. MS – Adjusted Mean Squares, F-value -- is the test statistic used to determine whether the term is associated with the response, P-value – is a probability that measures the evidence against the null hypothesis)

The main effects plot (76. Figure) shows that as layer thickness increases from 0.1 to 0.2 mm, surface roughness (Sa) increases. Thicker layers form higher "peaks" on the surface, and also the gap between two consecutive layers of the 3D printed part increases; therefore, surface roughness increases (76. Figure/a). we also observed that surface roughness decreases drastically when printing speed exceeds 40 mm/s. This is because the deposited filaments were stretched at a higher speed (60 and 80 mm/s), and the layers were smoothed. Also, increasing layer height reduces build time. This is not only because more material is deposited but also because, at a layer height of 0.2 mm, the gap between the two layers is more prominent, so printing finishes faster. Printing orientation does not affect build time (76. Figure/b).

The goal of these experiments was to find a correlation between surface roughness and bonding strength. But practically, we observed no evident correlation between these parameters. A possible reason could be the high melt temperature during overmolding (77. Figure). The polymer at 240 °C melts away the base plate's top layer irrespective of surface roughness. Although bonding strength plots show a correlation with all parameters, the standard deviation of bonding strength is higher than that of the changes in the mean values. Therefore, the observed bonding strength between a rib and a base plate has a negligible correlation with the surface roughness of the base plate. This motivates me to use other strategies and build more complex preforms so that the effect on bonding strength is more evident.

76. Figure Main effects plots for mean surface roughness; (b) Main effects plots for mean build time; (c) Main effects plots for mean bonding strength

77. Figure Resulted roughness (Sa) and bonding strength from 16 different test runs with different printing parameter combinations

4.1.3. The effect of infill density on bonding strength

As it previously was detailed, the preforms were printed with various FFF parameters. As expected, the infill density has an evident effect on the bonding strength between the base plate and the overmolded rib. Infill density has an apparent impact on the macrostructure of the 3D printed preforms. 78. Figure shows bonding strength and density as a function of infill density. The bonding strength of the 50% infill density specimen (20.2 MPa) is approximately three times higher than that of the 100% infill density specimen (5.8 MPa). The amount of material consumed increased with the increase in infill density. Thus, base plates with 50% and 100% infill density are 6.2 g and 13.2 g, respectively, which shows a 53% increase in mass. Besides, increasing the infill density increases the overall printing cost due to the

more prolonged printing time (0.78 h for 50% infill and 1.49 h for 100% infill) and the increased amount of material consumed.

78. Figure Effect of infill density on bonding strength as an exponential function and corresponding actual density as a linear function. The red line represents the measured experimental bonding strength value for the fully injection molded reference specimen (32 MPa). Symbols are experimental results; black solid and dotted lines are model predictions.

At an infill density of 100%, the rib comes into contact with the base plate, and there is simple adhesion between them (79. Figure), which leads to lower bonding strength (5.8 MPa). Lower infill densities cause bigger gaps in the base plate or, in other words, an increase in porosity. A comparison of preforms printed with 100%, 75%, 50% and 0% infill densities are shown in 79. Figure, and this clearly shows the changes in porosity. At 0% infill density, the bonding strength is basically equal to the bonding strength of the fully injection molded specimen (32 MPa). The bonding mechanism between these two limits depends on the porosity of the base plate and the penetration level of the incoming melt. So, with a 50% infill-density base plate (50% porous), a considerable amount of melt flows into these grid-like structures and forms a nearly full injection molded specimen. Therefore, there was an exponential increase in bonding strength (20.2 MPa). Due to the limits of the structural stability of FFF printed parts, infill densities below 50% cannot be created. As bonding strength increases exponentially, WE expect that the highest bonding strength of 32 MPa can theoretically be reached even before 0% infill density (78. Figure). Therefore, at around 30% infill density, these grid-like structures are fragile, which allows the melt to flow through them and melt them easily.

Consequently, the highest bonding strength of 32 MPa could be reached for the base plate with an infill density between 30% and 0%. Practically, it is not achievable as at an infill density below 50%, and the base plate breaks when it is removed from the FFF platform.

79. Figure Illustration of 3D-printed preforms with 100%, 75%, 50%, 0% infill densities, and images of debonded base plates at these infill densities.

When the ABS melt (79. Figure, blue color) was overmolded onto the low infill density preforms, the melt penetrated in the pores and resulted in better bonding between the base plate and the rib. However, the melt also flows through the pores and comes out through the preform's edges. Therefore, we let the overmolding melt flow in a specific region, then blocked its path and contained it inside the preform. Hence, the local infill density around the overmolding area was investigated further (explained in the next section).

4.1.4. Effect of local infill density on bonding strength

To stop the melt overflowing through the preform, we altered the infill density only along the ribs' contact area while keeping the other area of the preform at 100% density (80. Figure). As the commonly used slicing software was not efficient enough to create different infill densities in different areas. This way, we developed any infill density (100%, 75%, 50%, 25% and 0%) with triangular local infill patterns in a specific area for the overmolded rib.

80. Figure Illustration of local infill densities at the center of the base plate, where the overmolded rib will be in contact.

The preforms were printed with constant and variable FFF parameters, as mentioned in 7. A local infill density of 0% practically means a groove in the base plate. This groove is the bonding area. In all the other cases, grid-like structures with different local infill densities were created in the contact area. These grid-like structures are usually weaker than the full-density preform, so we call them "weak layer". When the rib is debonded, the weak layer with the local infill area breaks with the rib. The maximum bonding strength was observed at 0% infill density, where the contact surface area with the rib is the highest (429 mm²), and the rib has direct contact with the preform. 81. Figure shows a little but gradual increase in bonding strength from 100% (12.6 MPa) to 0% local infill density (17.4 MPa). The disadvantage of the melt overflowing in the preforms was also rectified by containing the overmolding melt inside the boundaries of the created local infill density part. We used the ANOVA test to determine the significance of local infill density on bonding strength. Since the *P*-value was less than 0.05, local infill density had a statistically significant effect on bonding strength at a confidence level of 95%.

81. Figure Effect of local infill density on bonding strength and the *p*-value from the ANOVA test

4.1.5. Effect of microstructure on bonding strength

We have proved that bonding strength increases with contact surface area. Thus, another possible solution to improve bonding between 3D-printed and overmolded elements is to create ridge and pit elements in the bonding area of the preform. These microstructures create a larger contact surface between the base plate and the overmolded rib. An increased contact surface area helps the overmolding melt to flow into these undercuts on the base plate to form mechanical interlocking. The mechanical force pulling out the overmolded parts from these ridges or pits lead to a substantial increase in the work of debonding. If the overmolded material thoroughly penetrates the pits or surrounds the ridges, it may not be possible to pull out the ribs without fracturing them.

We searched for several designs to establish a suitable microstructure with an increased contact surface area between the preforms and the ribs. However, we narrowed the possibilities down to few simple geometries due to FFF and injection molding limitations. we created geometrical features (positive and negative) on the top layers of the preform, where the overmolded rib is in contact with it (82. Figure).

Cases	Types	Front view	Side view	Contact surface area [mm ²]
Case 1 Positive Or Ridges	Type 1		373.37	
	Type 2		319.52	
	Type 3		289.56	
Case 2 Negative Or Pits	Type 4		429.02	
	Type 5		429.02	
	Type 6		301.49	

82. Figure Illustration of the ridges on and the pits in the FFF printed preforms along with their dimensions in mm and their corresponding contact surface area with the overmolded ribs

We considered two simple types of microstructures: ridges (positive) and pits (negative), and each one has three different patterns. The shape of the microstructures and the corresponding contact area of these elements significantly affected bonding strength, as the experimental results show (83. Figure). In the first case (ridges), when we analyzed the broken (debonded) samples, we found that the breakage happens between the microstructure and the preform rather than the preform and the ribs. WE assumed that the microstructure was debonded easily from the preform because of the weak interlayer adhesion between the printed layers. We compared the results of the positive structures with the negative ones.

In the second case (pits), the overmolding melt thoroughly penetrates the pits with the highest contact area (429.02 mm²), and it forms mechanical interlocking. This way, there is no way of pulling out the ribs without breaking the preforms. Here, the contact area has a more pronounced effect than the bonding strength of the printed interlayer. As seen in 83. Figure, the highest contact area is observed in Type 4 and Type 5 (429.02 mm²) microstructures, and the corresponding bonding strength for these types is the highest, 19.3 MPa and 20.2 MPa, respectively.

83. Figure Effect of microstructures on bonding strength. Symbols represent the actual contact area between the base plate and the ribs. The bars represent the experimental results for bonding strength.

4.1.6. Effect of fiber reinforcement on bonding strength

The concept of introducing fibers in the preforms and/or ribs is the next bonding strength improvement technique. The idea behind this is that the preform can be reinforced locally in the bonding area in the following way: a groove is created in the bonding area while the preform is printed, and then long CFs (60 mm length) is placed across this groove. The bottom of the groove was at the height of 0.4 mm. Then, when the preform was 1.2 mm thick (and consequently, the groove was 0.8 mm deep), eleven fiber rovings were placed manually across the groove (Step 3 – the white area is the groove). After this, the FFF continued to print the remaining 0.8 mm height on top of the CFs on both sides of the groove, as shown in 84. Figure. After the printing process, the preforms were hot pressed. The final preform can be seen in 85. Figure. we anticipated that a kind of mechanical interlocking is formed caused by fiber entanglement.

84. Figure Illustration of the production of the preform with the manually placed carbon fibers

The prepared short fiber reinforced ABS pellets were used to overmold these locally fiber-reinforced preforms (85. Figure). Four combinations were studied: Unreinforced preforms/unreinforced ribs (ABS/ABS), Unreinforced preforms/ CF reinforced ribs (ABS/ CF-ABS), Locally reinforced CF preforms/unreinforced ribs (L-CF ABS/ABS), Locally reinforced CF preforms/CF reinforced ribs. (L-CF ABS/ CF-ABS).

85. Figure Illustration of overmolding with fiber-reinforced printed preforms

As we reinforced the preforms locally with carbon fibers, we anticipated that the incoming overmolding melt should flow under the manually placed CFs in the preform. we expected a mechanical interlocking due to the fiber entanglement of the long fibers in the preform with the ribs' short fibers. However, the manual placement of CFs in the preform results in poor tension of the fibers. Therefore, these fibers were forced to bend by the overmolding melt, so less melt flowed under them. Thus, the bonding strength between the reinforced preforms and the ribs were not as high as expected (86. Figure).

Nevertheless, the bonding strength between preforms and reinforced ribs were higher than between preforms and unreinforced ribs. When CFs/ABS melt fills the mold's cavity, it forms a fountain flow, where the fibers are oriented along the direction of the melt (87. Figure). Consequently, the highly oriented CFs transfer more heat from the melt to the preform.

86. Figure Effect of fiber reinforcement on bonding strength

87. Figure Illustration of fountain flow in injection molding

In conclusion, except for the varying printing parameters, all the methods discussed in this section significantly impact bonding strength. The bonding strength of all the overmolding ABS specimens is shown in 88. Figure compared to the reference specimen's bonding strength. The obtained results showed that none of the proposed methods of bonding improvement produced the reference bonding strength, which is, practically, material strength. However, the proposed methods facilitate the increase in bonding strength between the printed and overmolded parts significantly. The trend is clear that the modified preforms showed better bonding strength than the unmodified ones. The best results were delivered when the "infill density" or "microstructure modification" methods were used. In these two cases, the bonding strength can be increased up to 20.2 MPa, which is an 83% increment compared to the original (plain) preforms (≈ 11 MPa), and it is much closer than what? to the strength of the reference specimen (≈ 32 MPa). WE obtained adequate results with the "local infill density" and "local fiber reinforcement" methods, which showed 57% and 45% bonding strength increment compared to the original preforms (17.3 and 16.0 MPa, respectively) — varying the printing process parameters resulted in negligible bonding strength increase.

88. Figure Comparison of the bonding strength of all methods in case of ABS

4.2. Overmolding and Overprinting of Polyamides

To rectify the poor interlayer adhesion between the printed FFF layers, we changed the printing method to selective laser sintering (SLS) as an alternative approach, where interlayer adhesion is much stronger than in the case of FFF. The different ways of curing in SLS can contribute to the interlayer entanglement reaction, which can substantially strengthen interlayer adhesion between adjacent layers by creating covalent bonds across the interface. We have tested what? with three different base plates from PA12: FFF printing with ready-made PA12 filament, FFF printing with filament made from recycled PA12 powder, laser sintering with virgin-PA12 powder.

4.2.1. Thermal results of Polyamides

The DSC heating of the PA12 filament, the recycled PA12 filament, and the virgin PA2200 powder were performed with identical heat-cool cycle conditions at the rate of 10 °C/min. From the DSC thermograms, the melting temperatures of the virgin PA12 filament, recycled PA12 filament were 178 °C and 177.7 °C, respectively. The crystallization temperatures measured on the cooling phase were 148.1 °C and 148.5 °C, respectively. The DSC trace for all the selected PA12 materials was consolidated and shown in 89. Figure - 91. Figure.

89. Figure DSC trace of polyamide filaments which is commercially bought, and filament made from recycled PA2200

90. Figure DSC trace of commercially available virgin PA2200 laser sintering powder, showing the sintering window (Region between the onset of melting and onset of crystallization)

91. Figure DSC trace of commercially available virgin recycled PA2200 laser sintering powder, showing the sintering window (Region between the onset of melting and onset of crystallization)

During the laser sintering (LS) process, the crystallization of the polymer starts during cooling. The crystallization process could lead to geometrical changes like shrinkage and warpage. Therefore, the temperature of the build cavity should be in a high temperature as possible so that the crystallization phase is suppressed during the build process. It is vital that the LS build cavity temperature must be higher than the crystallization temperature and below the melting point, so the powder does not fully melt in the build cavity. This temperature range is called a sintering window.

In this sintering window, the polymer is in a metastable region of super-cooled liquid. It's a zone where both solid and liquid phases coexist. If a polymer's crystallization and melting ranges overlap, the polymer would not be ideal for the LS process because it lacks a sufficiently wide LS sintering window. This sintering window of the polymer can be visualized in a simple heat-cool DSC trace. The polymers' sintering window is the region between the onset of the melting point (T_{im}) and the onset of the crystallization point (T_{ic}). In PA 2200 DSC trace, there is an adequate sintering region where the LS can be performed. In this case, the sintering window is approximately $\Delta T = 25^\circ\text{C}$.

The sintering window of PA2200 is reasonably located as the LS bed temperature falls in between their corresponding sintering window boundaries. For PA2200, the recommended bed temperature was 168 °C, and their sintering window is between 156.4 - 180.6°C. However, the shown DSC graphs are ideal measurement curves with high and linear heating/cooling rates (10 °C/min), according to the standard DIN 53765. But in LS reality, there are non-linear temperature rates. The cooling rates in the LS build cavity can be very much lower than the DSC environment (less than 1 °C/min).

4.2.2. Effect of the printing parameters on the surface roughness and the bonding strength

We produced 18 sets with different combinations of printing parameters following Taguchi's method analysis. Five specimens per set were printed and overmolded. The results were evaluated and given in 13. Table.

Set	FFF processing parameters			Results				
	v _{print} (mm/s)	h _{layer} (mm)	O _{print} (deg)	R _a (μm)		Bonding Strength (MPa)		Build time (hours)
				Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
1	30	0.1	0/90	9.17	1.62	20.76	3.19	3.58
2	50	0.1	0/90	8.34	1.11	17.54	2.37	2.17
3	70	0.1	0/90	9.76	1.41	12.49	2.18	1.53
4	30	0.2	0/90	13.69	2.30	10.30	3.21	1.92
5	50	0.2	0/90	17.49	3.12	8.69	2.16	1.17
6	70	0.2	0/90	16.06	2.12	11.82	1.56	0.83
7	30	0.3	0/90	14.26	0.88	5.38	3.02	1.17
8	50	0.3	0/90	14.79	1.58	8.12	2.39	0.80
9	70	0.3	0/90	15.23	2.54	10.40	4.93	0.58
10	30	0.1	45/-45	8.95	0.56	20.62	1.96	3.58
11	50	0.1	45/-45	9.91	1.51	17.02	3.76	2.17
12	70	0.1	45/-45	9.78	0.73	13.87	2.25	1.53
13	30	0.2	45/-45	17.51	0.56	10.92	1.65	1.92
14	50	0.2	45/-45	17.18	0.77	8.15	4.41	1.17
15	70	0.2	45/-45	14.74	0.56	10.30	1.80	0.83
16	30	0.3	45/-45	16.51	0.89	9.35	2.10	1.17
17	50	0.3	45/-45	12.75	2.88	7.11	4.36	0.80
18	70	0.3	45/-45	13.97	1.83	12.00	3.40	0.58

13. Table Design of Experiments for different printing parameters and the results

The obtained surface roughness data shows that it is in the range of 8.34 and 17.51 μm. The high standard deviation results from the instability of the desktop FFF printer and the contact-based surface roughness measurement. There were minor changes in the surface roughness with changing printing speed and printing orientation, so these printing parameters have no significant effect on the surface

roughness at a constant layer height (92. Figure). But always, the lower layer height samples show lower surface roughness because each raster width is very small at 0.1 mm, so the air gap between the raster remains the same at any printing speed. On the other hand, at a layer height of 0.2 mm, it is evident that surface roughness is much higher than in the case of a layer height of 0.1 mm with both printing orientations because of the broad air gap.

92. Figure Effect of layer height on the surface roughness at varying printing speeds and printing orientations

On the other hand, increasing the layer height decreases the bonding strength significantly at first but then remains almost identical. Printing speed and infill angle have a minor effect once again on this matter. This is shown in 93. Figure.

93. Figure Effect of layer height on the bonding strength at varying printing speeds and printing orientations

But there is no correlation between the surface roughness of the printed base plate and the bonding strength. That could have resulted from high melt temperature during overmolding, which is relatively high for the PA 12. Therefore, the top layer of the base plate melts away, and the surface texture loses its significance.

We performed an ANOVA to see the effects of printing parameters on the surface roughness and the bonding strength. In this analysis, the F value is calculated, which is the variance ratio; this is also defined as the mean square ratio due to a parameter and mean square of the error. If the values of the F ratio are greater than four, it is considered very important, and if it's smaller than 1, it is regarded as unimportant. Also, the contribution of the effect of each parameter on the response is shown in the following tables. 14. Table gives information on the ANOVA result, which shows the contribution of each parameter on the surface roughness. As is presented, layer height played a crucial role in surface roughness with a rate of 90.93%, followed by printing speed (0.06%) and printing orientation (0.022%).

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-value	P- value	Contribution
PS	2	0.000013	0.000007	0.04	0.962	0.06
LH	2	0.021118	0.010559	62.10	0.000	90.93
PO	1	0.000052	0.000052	0.30	0.592	0.022
Error	12	0.002040	0.000170			8.79
Total	17					100.00

14. Table The ANOVA for Surface Roughness

Regarding bonding strength, layer height was the most significant effect on bonding strength with a contribution of 70.62%, followed by printing speed (2.43%) and printing orientation (0.39%), as shown in 15. Table. Also, the build time is depended on the layer height and printing speed, as shown in 16. Table

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-value	P- value	Contribution
PS	2	0.16196	0.08098	0.55	0.591	2.43
LH	2	4.69859	2.34929	15.95	0.000	70.62
PO	1	0.02601	0.02601	0.18	0.682	0.39
Error	12	1.76701	0.14725			26.56
Total	17					100.00

15. Table The ANOVA for Bonding Strength

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-value	P- value	Contribution
PS	2	0.52276	0.026138	2034.99	0.000	37.41
LH	2	0.087308	0.043654	3398.67	0.000	62.48
PO	1	0.00000	0.00000	0.00	1.000	0.00
Error	12	0.000154	0.000013			0.11
Total	17					100.00

16. Table The ANOVA for build time

The main effect diagram (94. Figure) indicates that the surface roughness increases by increasing the layer thickness to 0.2 mm from 0.1 mm and then steadily goes down when the layer height is 0.3mm. Printing speed and infill angle have a minor effect on the surface roughness. The bonding strength drops overwhelmingly when the layer height reaches 0.2 mm and then continues to decline gradually. The bonding strengths of different infill angels are nearly the same. Increasing the printing speed to 50 mm/s decreases the bonding strength then increases it by increasing the speed to 70 mm/s.

94. Figure (a) Main effects plots for mean surface roughness; (b) Main effects plots for mean build time; (c) Main effects plots for mean bonding strength

4.2.3. Effect of FFF built microstructure on the bonding strength

Until now, the unmodified base plates without any structure are discussed. But it was clear that increasing the surface contact area increases the bonding strength. Therefore, considering this hypothesis, we have built similar microstructures on top of the FFF built, and SLS built base plates. The dimension of the top layer (i.e., the microstructures) was 60 mm x 2 mm, and it is placed precisely at the center of the base plate where the overmolded ribs will come into contact. Like the ABS experiment, six types of microstructures were built with the same dimensions.

The dimensional accuracy of the base plate has a significant effect on having a proper overmolding process. If the thickness exceeds the maximum tolerance limits, the mold's cavity and core parts do not match and prevent the overmolding process as the mold will not close. On the other hand, if the thickness is below the minimum tolerance limits, overflow occurs on the top layer of the base plate (95. Figure). It causes an increase in the debonding force significantly, but this is an undesired situation. So, the specimens with overflow were excluded from the evaluation. The successfully overmolded specimens were tensile tested, and their corresponding bonding strength results are shown in 96. Figure.

95. Figure Overflow on the top layer of the base plate

96. Figure Bonding strengths of FFF printed base plates

The results showed that the Type 1 specimen and their negative counterpart (type 4) showed no improvement compared to the unmodified specimen. In comparison, the other microstructure types showed significant improvement. The greatest improvement of 45% increase was seen in Type 2 microstructure (17.26 MPa), whereas the bonding strength of the unmodified specimen was 11.82 MPa. During the Type 2 microstructure, there were two types of debonding mechanism observed.

The overmolded material completely covered the ridges, and in certain areas the overmolded ribs are broken. This could be because the bonding was well established in that region, and the material strength was lower than the bonding strength (shown in 97. Figure/a).

The overmolded material completely covered the ridges and formed a perfect bond. But the adhesion between the baseplate and the microstructure was poor – so that the debonding occurs between the base plate and the microstructures rather than the microstructures and the ribs (Shown in 97. Figure/b). The interlayer adhesion between two consecutive FFF layers is usually poor, which is an important reason for this phenomenon. This poor trend is due to the fact that when a layer is deposited, the heat rapidly dissipates from the surface of the newly deposited layer. This heat loss restricts the intermolecular diffusion between the first layer and the subsequent layers, therefore decreasing the interlayer bonding. Hence building the microstructures in the SLS platform was the solution for this.

97. Figure a) Plane of debonding where the ribs got broken along certain region b) Debonding occurred where the FFF created microstructures were removed from the base plate

The nominal bonding strengths of negative (inward) structures were almost the same or had a minimal increase compared to the base plate without microstructures. During the overmolding process, base plates with negative structures have warped to their geometries under the holding pressure and temperature of injection molding (98. Figure). When the specimen was placed into the grips to perform a pull-out test, the base plate came back to its original unwarped form, but this could cause internal stress already and decrease the nominal bonding strength. This situation explained the achievement of lower nominal bonding strength in negative structures.

98. Figure FFF printed base plate with undercuts a) before overmolding b) after overmolding

We also observed that after debonding, the mechanical interlocking into undercuts was well established (99. Figure). That is why the fracture has taken place on the rib instead of basically coming out of the undercuts.

99. Figure Illustration of the fracture between the base plate with negative structure and rib

4.2.4. Effect of SLS built microstructure on the bonding strength

As the interlayer adhesion between FFF printed layers were poor, building the microstructures in the SLS platform was the following method to increase the bonding strength. The overall SLS process is

carried out in a controlled temperature environment, where the chamber temperature for PA was kept at 168 °C throughout the sintering process. Therefore, the interlayer adhesion is much stronger than the FFF process, as the layer was well fused.

The SLS specimen printed without any microstructure is considered an ‘unmodified’ specimen. At first glance, it is clear that the nominal bonding strength has been improved by having structures on the base plate as expected. 100. Figure shows that the microstructure geometry has an important effect on the bonding strength of the positive (outward) structures.

100. Figure Bonding strengths of SLS printed base plates

When we examined the positive structured base plates after overmolding, we found out two different breakout scenarios. The first scenario was that the plain of debonding was on the cross-sectional area between ridges and the base plate, meaning that the mechanical interlocking was well established (101. Figure/a). But the material strength was much weaker. Therefore, the overmolded ribs were broken, leaving some of the ribs on the base plate. The second one was that the debonding happened with the failure or broken microstructures. The cross-sectional area of these microstructures is fragile and weak, so that the microstructures were broken from the base plate (101. Figure/b).

101. Figure Plain of rupture over the top layer of structures (a) and on the interlayer (b)

The cross-sectional area of the ridges (102. Figure) plays a significant role in the bonding strength. Here in this case, the Type 3 pattern’s ridges have a lesser cross-sectional area than the Type 2, and for this reason, the ridges pulled out easily. To avoid this effect, WE should increase the contact area between the base plate and the ridge while increasing the strength of the microstructure itself. One way to do this is by increasing the surface area of the interface with many grooves, holes, or bosses. A porous substrate may also provide tiny holes into which the overmold material can migrate to create a mechanical bond.

102. Figure Illustration of the cross-sectional area of a ridge

The bonding strengths of the negative (inward) specimens were also improved compared to the unmodified ones. When the broken specimens were analyzed, we observed that the mechanical interlocking has occurred besides bonding (103. Figure). The adhesion between the base plate and the overmolded rib was weaker, even though mechanical interlocking was established. The geometry of the structure and the contact area has a more significant effect on keeping them together. The highest nominal bonding strength was 13.96 MPa with the Type 6 pattern, and the lowest one was 10.84 for Type 5.

103. Figure The mechanical interlocking between the base plate and rib a) before pull-off b) after tear-off test

4.2.5. Comparison of FFF and SLS Technologies on Overmolding

FFF technology is an unstable printing process, and this gives a lower-dimensional accuracy compared to SLS technology. This inconsistent accuracy could help to have more contact area for ridges and increase the nominal bonding strength. As shown in 104. Figure, the uncertainty in the dimensional accuracy of FFF parts gives rise to a tighter fit with the overmolded ribs, which ultimately increased the bonding strength. Meanwhile, in SLS, the dimensional accuracy of the laser-sintered PA2200 was much better, with 1.95 mm as the lowest thickness and no specimens having thickness more than 2 mm.

104. Figure Effect of positive (Outward) structures on bonding strength

As is observed in 105. Figure, base plates with negative structures had slightly higher nominal bonding strength with SLS technology. The reason could be that the degree of warpage was higher for FFF parts than SLS ones, which means that more internal stresses were induced in the base plates, which causes the bonding strength to drop.

105. Figure Effect of negative (Inward) structures on bonding strength

4.2.6. Comparison of Virgin and Recycled FFF filament

We reached the higher surface roughness, and the bonding strength results by printing base plates with a recycled PA filament. The changes in flow property of the recycled filament could be a reason for higher surface roughness, as it is known from the literature. The lower melt fluidity causes less material flow from the nozzle, and this situation increases the air gaps between printed layers. Therefore, the printed part has a much rougher surface quality (106. Figure). Furthermore, during the powder's extrusion and granulation, there are always undesired impurities that also affect the surface texture.17. Table shows the corresponding surface roughness values of recycled filament base plates.

106. Figure Effect of FFF printed base plates' material on surface roughness

		FFF Printing Parameters			Results			
Set	Printing Orientation [°]	Layer Height [mm]	Printing Speed [mm/s]	Printing Time [min.]	Surface Roughness (Ra) [µm]		Bonding Strength [MPa]	
					Mean	SD	Mean	SD
1	45-90	0.2	70	50	26.52	4.50	22.45	1.50
2	0-90	0.2	70	50	27.05	4.85	21.28	4.85
3	0-90	0.3	70	35	32.15	2.07	16.89	2.25

17. Table Experimental Design for Recycled Filament and Results

Virgin and recycled filaments show different degree of crystallization under the same holding pressure and holding time. Different degree of crystallization provides specimens with the different bonding strength during overmolding. The degree of crystallization is directly proportional to the degree of shrinkage in semi-crystalline materials. The base plate printed with a recycled filament has lower shrinkage because of its lower degree of crystallization. So that means less internal stress related to warped shape occurs on the base plate compared to the one printed with a virgin filament, and it helps to receive higher debonding forces (107. Figure).

107. Figure Effect of FFF printed base plates' material on bonding strength

Conclusions

This task has focused on the development and validation of various methods to enhance the bonding strength between overmolded and printed parts, with particular emphasis on the use of fiber reinforcement, microstructural modifications, and numerical simulations to predict bonding outcomes. The detailed examination of these methods has provided significant insights into the mechanics and optimization strategies required to achieve superior bonding performance.

The experimental findings indicate that locally reinforcing preforms with carbon fibers significantly impacts the bonding strength between overmolded parts. Despite the initial assumption that manually placed carbon fibers would facilitate better mechanical interlocking, practical challenges such as poor tension and bending of fibers led to suboptimal bonding outcomes. Nevertheless, reinforced preforms exhibited higher bonding strengths than their unreinforced counterparts, particularly when using methods that promote fiber orientation along the melt flow direction. This is attributed to the enhanced load transfer and reduced stress concentrations at the interface provided by the fibers, which help in better distributing the applied loads.

Among the methods tested, microstructure modifications such as increased infill density demonstrated the most significant improvements. Specifically, methods such as "infill density" and "microstructure modification" resulted in bonding strength increments up to 20.2 MPa, representing an 83% improvement over the original preforms. Other methods like "local infill density" and "local fiber reinforcement" showed 57% and 45% increments, respectively. These results underscore the effectiveness of these techniques in enhancing the bonding strength, despite the fact that none of the methods achieved the reference bonding strength of approximately 32 MPa. The increased infill density method particularly stands out as it provides a denser network of bonds within the material, which translates to better adhesion and mechanical interlocking between the preform and the overmolded part.

Additionally, the incorporation of fiber reinforcement, although challenged by practical issues, demonstrated potential benefits in mechanical interlocking and load distribution. Future studies might explore automated or advanced fiber placement techniques to overcome the issues of poor tension and bending, thereby maximizing the reinforcement benefits.

To predict bonding strength more accurately, a novel calculation method was developed that combines analytical and numerical approaches. This method accounts for the spatial and temporal unevenness of temperature distribution at the interface. The simulation of the overmolding process, validated through mechanical testing, demonstrated good agreement with experimental results, with a prediction error of only 7%. The results indicated that higher melt and mold temperatures correlate with increased bonding strength. This correlation is crucial because it provides a clear direction for optimizing processing parameters to achieve better bonding.

The method's effectiveness was further demonstrated through its application to semi-crystalline polymers like polypropylene (PP). By fitting the WLF (Williams-Landel-Ferry) equation to measured rheological values, the method accurately predicted the degree of healing and bonding strength of the interface. The validation against experimental data showed that the calculated bonding strengths for both homopolymer and random copolymer PP were within the standard deviation of the measured strengths, confirming the method's reliability. This success in modeling semi-crystalline polymers underscores the versatility and robustness of the developed numerical approach.

The modeling approach considered the intricate interplay of temperature, pressure, and time on the molecular diffusion and healing processes at the interface. By accurately capturing these dynamics, the model provides a reliable tool for predicting bonding outcomes under various processing conditions. This capability is particularly valuable for process optimization and quality control in industrial applications.

Deviations from the DoA

We presume that the present report covers all the aspects of Task 1.1, without deviations from GA.

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